

**Physico-Chemical and Computational Studies of
Bacterial Carbohydrates**

by

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ABSTRACT

Physico-chemical and computational studies of bacterial carbohydrates

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This thesis is composed of two investigations: the structure of the capsular polysaccharide expressed on the surface of *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 and the *Clostridium bolteae* capsular polysaccharide conformation by molecular modelling. The majority of gas gangrene development is due to *Clostridium perfringens*. *Clostridium bolteae* was found present in the intestinal tract of children diagnosed with autism and not present in the control group. Developing a vaccine by targeting the capsular polysaccharide of virulent strains will help prevent the development of these detrimental infections. However, in order to produce a vaccine, the structure of the capsular polysaccharide must first be determined. The *Clostridium perfringens* capsular polysaccharide has yet to be fully characterized but has been found thus far to be an oligosaccharide repeat unit containing $\rightarrow 4$)- β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 3)-D-Gal(1 \rightarrow , \rightarrow 2)-[β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- α -D-Gal-(1 \rightarrow , \rightarrow 4)- α -D-GalNAc-(1 \rightarrow and \rightarrow 3)-[β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 2)]- β -D-Man-(1 \rightarrow . The conformation of the *Clostridium bolteae* polysaccharide was found to be a right-handed seven-unit repeating helix.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, NOMENCLEATURE AND SYMBOLS

α	Alpha
β	Beta
δ	Chemical shift (in ppm)
1D	One Dimensional
2D	Two Dimensional
3D	Three Dimensional
AA	Alditol acetate
aDm-aLr	Methyl 4'- <i>O</i> -(3- <i>O</i> -methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside [3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-Rhap-OMe]
aDm-bDr	Methyl 4'- <i>O</i> -(3- <i>O</i> -methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- β -D-rhamnopyranoside [3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-Rhap-OMe]
aDm-bLr	Methyl 4'- <i>O</i> -(3- <i>O</i> -methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- β -L-rhamnopyranoside [3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -L-Rhap-OMe]
aDr-bDm	Methyl 3'- <i>O</i> -(4- <i>O</i> -methyl- α -D-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-mannopyranoside [4-OMe- α -D-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-Manp-OMe]
aLr-aDm	Methyl 3'- <i>O</i> -(4- <i>O</i> -methyl- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside [4-OMe- α -L-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe]
APC	Antigen-presenting cell
bDm-aDr	Methyl 4'- <i>O</i> -(3- <i>O</i> -methyl- β -D-mannopyranosyl)- α -D-rhamnopyranoside [3-OMe- β -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap-OMe]
bDr-aDm	Methyl 3'- <i>O</i> -(4- <i>O</i> -methyl- β -D-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside [4-OMe- β -D-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe]
bLr-aDm	Methyl 3'- <i>O</i> -(4- <i>O</i> -methyl- β -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside [4-OMe- β -L-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe]
<i>C. bolteae</i>	<i>Clostridium bolteae</i>
<i>C. perfringens</i>	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>
COSY	Correlation spectroscopy
CPS	Capsular polysaccharide

Gal	Galactose
GalNAc	<i>N</i> -acetyl galactosamine
GC	Gas chromatography
GC-MS	Gas chromatography – mass spectrometry
Glc	Glucose
GlcNAc	<i>N</i> -acetyl glucosamine
HMBC	Heteronuclear Multiple Bond Correlation spectroscopy
HOD	Partially deuteriated water ($^1\text{H} - \text{O} - ^2\text{H}$)
HSQC	Heteronuclear Single Quantum Correlation spectrometry
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
IgM	Immunoglobulin M
Kdo	Ketodeoxyoxonate (2-keto-3-deoxy- <i>D</i> -manno-octulosonic acid)
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide
LTA	Lipoteichoic Acid
Man	Mannose
MD	Molecular dynamic
MHC	Major histocompatibility complex
MurNAc	<i>N</i> -acetylmuramic acid
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
NOESY	Nuclear Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy
PES	Potential energy surface
PMAA	Partially methylated alditol acetate
Rha	Rhamnose
T_H cells	T-helper cells
TI-2	Thymus-independent type 2 antigen
TOCSY	Total Correlation Spectroscopy
WTA	[Cell] Wall Teichoic Acid

CARBOHYDRATE STRUCTURES

α -D-Glucose (Glc)

β -D-Glucose (Glc)

β -D-Galactose (Gal)

***N*-acetyl- β -D-Galactosamine (GalNAc)**

α -D-Mannose (Man)

β -D-Rhamnose (Rha)

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Carbohydrates

1.1.1. General classification

Carbohydrates are ubiquitous in nature and are used in various ways including as a source of energy, a structural component and cell signalling.^[1, 2] Classically the name was derived as “hydrates of carbon”, giving the molecular formula $C_n(H_2O)_m$ where n = number of carbons present and $m = n -$ the number of linked sites.^[1] The term “carbohydrate” may incorrectly imply that the carbons are attached to water molecules, especially upon seeing the previous chemical formula; a more appropriate definition is that carbohydrates are polyhydroxy compounds.^[1, 3]

1.1.2. Different projections of carbohydrates

Carbohydrate structures are often drawn in one of three forms: the Fisher projection for acyclic structures, where the horizontal line representing the atoms projecting out-of-plane towards you and the vertical line projecting the atoms into and behind the plane of the paper; the Haworth projection for cyclic structure which is favoured by biochemists; and the line drawing of cyclic structure which displays spatial information and is a more realistic representation of saccharides (Figure 1).^[1, 4] The Fisher projection can be transformed in to the three-dimensional (3D) structure by having all substituents at the left of the backbone in the Fisher projection pointing upwards in the 3D structure and, vice-versa, the substituents to the right would point downwards in the 3D structure (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Different representations of α -D-glucose. The acyclic form is shown in the (A) Fisher projection and its (B) wedge-line-dash form. The cyclic pyranose forms are displayed in (C) the Fisher projection, (D) the Haworth projection and (E) a line drawing with the glucose in the 4C_1 chair configuration. [1, 4, 5]

Figure 2. Conversion of D-glucose from the acyclic (Fisher projection) to the cyclic structure (Haworth projection).[6]

1.1.3. Absolute configuration

The position of the hydroxyl group at the highest chiral carbon (C*), typically the second last carbon of the chain – such as C5 in a hexose, determines the absolute configuration of the saccharide. [1, 7] The carbohydrate is in the *dextro* (D) configuration if the hydroxyl group of the C* is pointing to the right in the Fisher projection (“pointing downwards” in a 3D cyclic structure); the *laevo* (L) configuration is when the C* hydroxyl group is pointing to the left in the Fisher projection (“pointing upwards” in a 3D cyclic structure) (Figure 3). [1, 7, 8]

Figure 3. The structure of the triose compounds. Note that the aldose glyceraldehyde is a chiral compound whereas the ketose 1,3-dihydroxyacetone is achiral. [5]

1.1.4. Conformation of carbohydrates

When the carbon chain is long enough, the saccharide can form a stable cyclic structure with an endocyclic oxygen through an intramolecular nucleophilic addition of a hydroxyl group with the carbonyl functional group (Figure 2). [5] This will result either in the either five-membered ring furanose or the six-membered ring pyranose; the name of these structures are derived from the chemical compounds, furan and pyran, which the cyclic structures resembles (Figure 4). [5]

These cyclic structures can exist in different conformations. From the least to the greatest stability, pyranose can exist in either the half-chair (*H*), boat (*B*), skewed/twist-boat (*S*) or in the chair (*C*) conformation; typically pyranose compounds are found in the chair conformation as it is the least energetic and most stable, thus more favourable, conformation (Figure 6).^[9, 10] The furanose can exist in either the envelope (*E*) or twist (*T*) conformation; the energy difference between the two furanose conformations is small, unlike the case for pyranose (Figure 7).^[4] The numbered carbon position, and ‘O’ for the endocyclic oxygen, are superscripted if that position is pointing up (raised above the plane of the ring); vice-versa, the position is subscripted for the position which is pointing below the plane of reference.

There are two available bonds on the carbon, which are not involved in the cyclic formation, where they are classified to be either in the axial or equatorial position for the chair conformation, which is the most stable conformation.^[10] The axial position is drawn on the *y*-axis and follows the same direction as the “indent” where the carbon of the ring is (pointing either up or down along the *y*-axis). The equatorial position is drawn in the *z*-axis near the centre of the ring (the equator of the ring); the equatorial bond is parallel to the second cyclic bond from its cyclic carbon position on the opposite side of the ring (Figure 5).^[10]

The larger substituents are preferably located at the equatorial position so that the substituent is further away from other atoms; this results in less steric hindrance and ring stress which would otherwise occur due to interaction between the atoms at the axial position.^[4] For a typical pyranose, the equatorial position preference of carbon #5 (*C*5) influences whether a pyranose is in the ⁴*C*₁ or ¹*C*₄ conformation; for example, a pyranose

in its D-configuration (when the bulky substituent of C5 is pointing “up”) is often in the 4C_1 chair conformation whereas the L-configuration (when C5’s substituent is pointing “down”) prefers the 1C_4 chair conformation so that the C6 substituent is in the equatorial position (Figure 2 and Figure 8).^[10]

Figure 4. A structural comparison of the cyclic hexose in its (A) pyranose and (C) furanose conformations to its eponyms (B) pyran and (D) furan.

Figure 5. Positions of the axial (A) and equatorial (E) bonds in the 4C_1 and 1C_4 chair conformations. A sphere is shown to show the xyz coordinates with the axial position defined along the y -axis and the equatorial position is along the equator of the sphere.

Figure 6. A few examples of the different conformations of the cyclic pyranose. The cyclic structure can exist in the chair (C), boat (B), half-chair (H) or a skewed/twist-boat (S) form. The superscript denotes the atom positioned above from the reference plane (in grey) and the subscript denotes the atom positioned below the reference plane. ^[4, 6, 9-11] Note that carbon #4 is directly behind carbon #1 in the figure for 2S_0 .

Figure 7. A few examples of the different conformations of the cyclic furanose. The cyclic structure can exist in either the envelope (E) or twist (T) form. The superscript denotes the atom positioned above from the reference plane (in grey) and the subscript denotes the atom positioned below the reference plane. ^[4, 6, 9-11]

* α/β configuration is the relationship between O1 and the hydroxyl group which will form the (hemi)acetal upon the ring closure, in this case O4

Figure 8. Cyclization of D-glucose to its furanose form in the chair configuration by rotation of the bond within the Fisher projection.^[6]

1.1.5. Coupling constant and the Karplus equation

The Karplus equation is a quadratic formula, $J(\phi) = A \cos^2 \phi + B \cos \phi + C$ where A, B and C are constants that are dependent on the molecule, that relates the size of the coupling constant over 3 bonds (${}^3J_{a,b}$), in Hz, as a function of the dihedral angle (ϕ , in $^\circ$) of the vicinal protons (or other atoms); this equation is normally displayed as a plot to show the relationship of 3J and the ϕ . As seen in the following figure, if both vicinal protons are *trans*-diaxial – that is the dihedral angle (θ) is $\sim 180^\circ$ – the 3J value is large, within 7 to 12 Hz range. However, if at least one of the protons is in the equatorial position, then the dihedral angle is $\sim 60^\circ$, giving a small 3J value between 1 to 4 Hz; and if the 3J value is < 3 Hz, it will appear as an unresolved doublet.^[8, 12, 13]

Figure 9. A plot of the Karplus equation. (A) A general plot of the Karplus equation to show the relationship between the vicinal dihedral angle and the coupling constant. Also shown is a figure of D-glucose in its' (B) α - and (C) β -configuration with a Newman projection of the C1-C2 bond to display the dihedral angle (θ , in $^\circ$) between H1 and H2 and its' effect on the peak (doublet) splitting due to 3J -value value.

1.1.6. Anomeric configuration

When the carbohydrate is in its cyclic form, there's a new functional group present which is not possible in its acyclic form: the hemiacetal/hemiketal group, if looking at an unlinked monosaccharide, or an acetal/ketal functional group if that carbohydrate is linked (Figure 10).^[4, 8] The anomeric configuration has two configurations: alpha (α) and beta (β), and it is determined by the structural relationship in the acyclic form between the hydroxyl group which forms the endocyclic oxygen by attacking the carbonyl group, O4 in a furanose and O5 in a pyranose, and the position the newly hydroxyl group, the anomeric oxygen (formally the carbonyl group, typically O1 in a aldose and O2 in a ketose), takes in the hemiacetal functional group (Figure 2).^[8, 10]

In the acyclic structure, if the endocyclic and anomeric oxygen are *cis* to each other, the sugar is considered to be in the α -configuration; vice-versa, if the two are *trans*, the carbohydrate is considered to be in the β -anomeric configuration.^[8] For the most-stable cyclic structure (4C_1 for D-sugars and 1C_4 for L-sugars), the opposite is true due to the rotation of the C4/C5 (ring closing bond) from the intramolecular attack (Figure 2).

For most cases in the most-stable closed ring structure, the anomeric oxygen in the α -anomer is in the downward position whereas the anomeric oxygen in the β -anomer is in the upward position; however, be hesitant on basing the anomeric configuration based on the axis position (as in being either the axial or equatorial position) as there are scenario where this fails such as in a ring-flip of the most stable structure, such as the 1C_4 form of D-glucose where 4C_1 is its most stable form, as it will appear as the opposite anomeric configuration even though they are the same (Figure 11).

Figure 10. The (A) hemiacetal and (B) acetal functional groups in a pyranose. The dotted lines are displayed to help the visualization of the rest of the cyclic structure of the pyranose.

Figure 11. Chair conformations of β -D-glucose. Both the 4C_1 and 1C_4 representations of glucose are still in its β -configuration; the 4C_1 configuration is the most stable form of β -glucose.

1.1.7. Structural equilibrium and the anomeric effect

Due to both the reversibility of the cyclic structure to its acyclic form, each free monosaccharide exists in equilibrium with five forms in solution: the acyclic structure and the cyclic structures (furanose and pyranose) with both cyclic structures existing in the α - and β -anomeric configurations (Figure 12).^[8] The equilibrium shift for the major stable product as either the α - or β -configuration, as well as to the furanose or pyranose conformation, is dependent on various factors such steric hindrance and the anomeric effect.^[10]

Figure 12. Various D-Glucose structures in equilibrium.^[8]

The ratio of the anomeric configuration as well as the conformation of the structure depends on various parameters such as the solvent present, the temperature and the influence of the hydroxyl group position.^[8] The anomeric effect, also known as the Edward-Lemieux effect, occurs with the presence of the pattern C-Y-C-X where Y is an atom with a non-bonding orbital (i.e. lone pair, such as N, O and S) and X is an electronegative substituent; this effect which gives greater structural stability when the electronegative substituent, such as the anomeric oxygen, is present in the axial position.

[4, 8, 10, 14]

There are two explanations behind this phenomenon: the first is that when the electronegative substituent is in the axial position, there is a partial cancellation of the dipole moment whereas, in the equatorial position, the dipole moment is additive which leads to a slightly less stable form (Figure 13).^[8, 10] The second explanation relates to the molecular orbital where the filled non-bonding orbital (n) of the lone pair atom (Y) interacts with the unfilled anti-bonding orbital (σ^*) of the C-X bond; this interaction (hyperconjugation) only occurs if the n & σ^* overlap which is only possible if the electronegative substituent X is anti-periplanar (in the axial position) of the lone pair Y atom (Figure 14).^[4, 8, 10]

Figure 13. The partial dipole moment of anomers. (A) There is a partial cancellation of the dipole moment which causes the X(axial) anomer to be slightly more stable than (B) the X(equatorial) anomer.

Figure 14. The molecular orbital of anomers. (A) shows the hyperconjugation of the non-bonding (n) orbital with the anti-bonding (σ^*) when the C-X bond is in the axial configuration whereas (B) does not have this interaction as the two orbitals do not overlap.

1.1.8. Polysaccharide conformation

The polysaccharide chain will assume a conformation based on their linkage site(s) as well as the rotation along the glycosidic bond; the common conformation is either a helical- or ribbon-like structure.^[15, 16] A prediction of the conformation of the polysaccharide structure can be made by observing the geometrical relationship^[15] by displaying the linkage sites (Figure 15). For example: if the polysaccharide was composed of only zig-zag repeats (such as 4-linked β -D-glucose), the structure would be a ribbon type whereas the presence of U-turn repeats would likely form a helical structure.^[15, 16]

When characterizing a helical structure, there are three variables reported: n , the number of repeating units per turn; h , the height between two repeating units in a turn along the helix axis; t , the angle of rotation for each monosaccharide in the repeating unit ($360^\circ/n$); and p , the pitch height of each turn ($n \cdot h$).^[6, 15] Helical structures do have chirality and this can be shown by assigning a sign to either n or h where the positive sign refers to the structure being a right-handed helix, in which the rotation occurs clockwise (turns to the right), and the negative sign referring to the helix being left-handed (Figure 16).^[15]

Figure 15. Geometrical relationship of different linked monosaccharides. (A) A zig-zag relationship in a 3-linked α -D-mannopyranose; (B) zig-zag in a 4-linked β -D-rhamnopyranose; (C) twist in a 2-linked β -D-glucopyranose and (D) a U-turn in a 4-linked α -D-glucopyranose.^[15, 16]

Figure 16. A right-handed six-fold helix. It is right handed as the helix turns clockwise when going up.^[15]

1.2. Gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria

1.2.1. Differentiation by Gram staining

When differentiating and identifying bacteria, a Gram stain is performed and the majority are classified as being either gram-positive or gram-negative. The Gram's stain method is done by staining the cells with the primary dye 'crystal violet' followed by iodine, which complexes with the crystal violet, followed by a decolourizer (typically ethanol or acetone) and then the counter stain such as safranin.^[17]

Gram-positive cells retain the crystal violet-iodine complex, which is a purple colour, due to the thick peptidoglycan layer and the cross-linking teichoic acids present; gram-negative cells, on the other hand, is stained with the counterstain's colour, such as the pink of safranin, as the crystal violet-iodine complex is lost due to the disruption of the outer membrane from the decolourizer.^[17, 18]

1.2.2. Cell wall

The peptidoglycan layer, also known as murein, is composed of repeating *N*-acetyl glucosamine (GlcNAc) and *N*-acetyl muramic acid (MurNAc) with a β -1,4 link^[19]; the 3-position of the MurNAc has an oligopeptide unit attached to its lactic acid component which frequently cross-links to the nearby strands.^[19] As stated previously, gram-positive organisms are known to have a much thicker peptidoglycan layer than gram-negative bacteria.^[17, 19]

1.2.3. Gram-negative: outer membrane and lipopolysaccharide

Another significant between the two Gram classifications is the presence of the outer membrane which is present only in gram-negative bacteria^[19] (Figure 17). The outer membrane has the presence of lipopolysaccharide (LPS), another component unique to gram-negative bacteria.^[19] The LPS is composed of three parts: lipid A, core oligosaccharide unit and the O-specific antigen.^[20] Lipid A is an endotoxic glycopospholipid which, in *Escherichia coli*, is composed of phosphorylated glucosamine units with *N*-linked β -hydroxymyristic acid (a n-tetradecanoic acid (C_{14:0}) fatty acid).^[19, 20] The lipid A component, present on the outer membrane, connects to the non-repeating core oligosaccharide region by the compound ketodeoxyoxonate (Kdo, 3-deoxy-D-*manno*-octulosonic acid), which is linked to other atypical carbohydrates such as L-*glycero*-D-*manno*-heptoses; both of which may have other moieties present such as phosphates and phosphoryl ethanolamine.^[19, 21] The O-specific antigen is composed of repeating O-linked oligosaccharides in which the composition differs between species.^[19]

Figure 17. A general depiction of the gram-negative (left) and gram-positive (right) cell wall. Adapted from Esko et al., 2009^[19]; Ruiz et. al, 2009^[20] and Brown et al., 2013^[22].

1.2.4. Gram-positive: cell wall teichoic acids and lipoteichoic acids

Most gram-positive bacteria have an anionic repeating unit known as teichoic acids which are composed of repeating units of either glycerol or ribitol linked with a phosphate group; positive cationic groups, such as D-alanine, or positive/neutral saccharides can be found attached along the glycerol/ribitol backbone.^[19, 22] The teichoic acids can be found in two locations: as part of the inner membrane, which are known as lipoteichoic acids (LTA), or on the cell wall attached to approximately every tenth MurNAc unit of the peptidoglycan, known as wall teichoic acids (WTA).^[19]

The precise function for LTA and WTA remains yet unknown but it has been experimentally determined that, for WTA in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, is required for resistance against β -lactam derived antibiotics^[23] and mediate with external stresses.^[23-25]

1.2.5. Capsular polysaccharide

Bacteria are able to produce a capsule by producing many strands of polysaccharide, known as the capsular polysaccharide (CPS); it is an important virulence factor in pathogenic bacteria as the CPS aids in the protection of the microorganism from its environment, including the prevention of phagocytosis by a macrophage, and other factors such as adhesion to cell surfaces for colonization.^[19, 26-28] As the name implies, the CPS is composed of many repeating saccharide units; due to the high molecular weight of the CPS structure, along with the repetition of the subunits, most CPS extract by themselves are poor long-term immunogenic compounds as injecting most pure CPS results in no production of immunological memory cells.^[29, 30]

1.3. The Clostridiaceae family

The members of the Clostridiaceae family, which encompasses the *Clostridium* genus, are composed of bacteria in which the vast majority are known to be sporulating, gram-positive rod-shaped obligate anaerobe.^[31] The *Clostridium* genus is well known to contain many toxigenic members that produces exotoxins such as *Clostridium botulinum* and *Clostridium tetani* ^[32, 33], both which produces one of the most potent biological neurotoxins to humans known thus far, and *Clostridium difficile*; the latter which is an issue in the hospital setting as it is one of the leading nosocomial (hospital-acquired) infection^[34] and the cause of the majority of antibiotic-associated diarrhoea^[35, 36] and can cause pseudomembranous colitis^[34] in severe cases.

1.3.1. *Clostridium bolteae*

Clostridium bolteae, formally classified as part of unidentified isolate of *Clostridium clostridioforme*^[37], was named in honour of Ms. Ellen R. Bolte^[37], who started off the research in bacteria playing a role in the development of late-onset autism with her hypothesis that *Clostridium tetani*^[38] could be one of the causes for a subset of children due to the tetanus neurotoxin by the colonized species.

C. bolteae has the phenotype that is common for the members of the majority of the family Clostridiaceae; that is to say it is an obligate anaerobic, sporulating gram-positive bacilli^[31].

1.3.1.1. Determined capsular polysaccharide structure of *Clostridium bolteae*

The capsular polysaccharide for *C. bolteae* strains 14578 and 16351^[12] were identified, by a fellow member of the Dr. Monteiro research group, to be a disaccharide repeating unit with $[-\rightarrow 3)-\alpha\text{-D-Manp}(1\rightarrow 4)-\beta\text{-D-Rhap}(1\rightarrow)]_n$.

1.3.2. *Clostridium perfringens*

Clostridium perfringens, formally known as *Clostridium welchii*, is an obligate anaerobic, spore-producing, gram-positive bacilli bacterium that is widely found in the environment, such as in soil, and as part of the normal flora of many mammalian gastrointestinal tracts, including humans.^[39, 40]

C. perfringens is well-known as one of the most prevalent bacteria which cause gas gangrene (clostridial myonecrosis), which has a high mortality rate if not treated quickly; death can occur within 48 hours and as little as 12 hours.^[41, 42] There is necrosis of the skeletal muscle tissue (myonecrosis) at the local site of infection which is often followed by edema, formation of blisters and production of gas bubbles as the infection continues; if not treated promptly, the person will need to amputate the site of infection otherwise they will die due to shock or organ failure.^[41-45] Treatment for gas gangrene includes the removal of the infected area and large doses of antibiotics, typically penicillin or clindamycin.^[41]

1.3.2.1. Determined capsular polysaccharide structures of *Clostridium perfringens*

In previous studies, there were two strains of *Clostridium perfringens* which had their structures identified by NMR: Hobbs 5^[46], which has a linear hexasaccharide structure $[\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-Galp-(1}\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GalpNAc-(1}\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GlcpA-(1}\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GlcpNAc-(1}\rightarrow 2)\text{-}\alpha\text{-D-Galp-(1}\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-Manp-(1}\rightarrow]_n$; and Hobbs 10^[47], a pentasaccharide repeat with a branched glucose unit: $[\rightarrow 4)\alpha\text{-D-Galp-(1}\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-Galp-(1}\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-Glcp-(1}\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\alpha\text{-IdopA-(1}\rightarrow 3)\text{-}[\beta\text{-D-Glcp-(1}\rightarrow 6)]\text{-}\beta\text{-D-GalpNAc-(1}\rightarrow]_n$.

1.4. Interaction with the immune system

1.4.1. B and T cells

The B cells and T cells are two important lymphocytes involved in protecting the host against foreign materials. T cells, which are matured in the Thymus, have a receptor which recognizes an antigen through the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecule present. The B cells, matured in the bone marrow, have antibodies present on its membrane which binds with an antigen that the antibody has an affinity for.^[26]

Antigen-presenting cells (APCs), such as B cells, dendritic cells and macrophages, have a class II MHC molecule present on their membrane. When a T-helper cell (T_H cell) encounters a APC-antigen complex, it releases several cytokines to elicit an immune response; this cytokine release is essential for long-term immunity.^[26]

The antibodies present on the B cells membrane in the primary response against an unknown antigen is typically immunoglobulin M (IgM). The presence of specific cytokines released by T cells stimulates the production of both memory B and memory T cells and

initiates a class change in the progeny B cells, expressing immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies specific for the antigen encountered.^[26]

B cells expressing IgG antibodies are part of the secondary immune response. Upon exposure to the foreign antigen once again, after a few weeks, there is a quicker and stronger immune response. This is due to the large amount of IgG proliferated from the primary response and the IgG B cells persists in the body for a longer period of time, in years, in the body than IgM B cells, which can last for a couple of weeks at the most ^[26, 48-50]

1.4.2. Conjugated Capsular Polysaccharide Vaccines

Most pure CPS are typically poor antigens and are classified as a Thymus-independent type 2 (TI-2) antigen; this means that an immune response only occurs through the stimulation of mature B cells but it is unable to stimulate the T_H cells nor activates the immature B cells. As a consequence, there is no long-term immunity as there is no cytokines causing the proliferation of memory B cells and no class change to IgG.^[26, 30]

Conjugation of the CPS to an antigenic carrier, such as a protein or a toxoid like the mutant diphtheria toxin CRM₁₉₇, has been shown to produce long-term immunity. This is due to the carrier being a Thymus-dependent (TD) antigen, which stimulates T_H cells to interact with the B cells, unlike TI-2 antigens; as the T_H cells are now interacting, memory B cells are produced.^[26, 48, 51, 52]

1.5. Computational chemistry

1.5.1. Background

The basis of computational chemistry is to find answers for theoretical questions which may be difficult, costly or impossible to observe physically, such as how would a molecule in its transition state appear, what would be the preferred conformation of a molecule at specific temperatures, in different solvents and the effect of overall conformation of the molecule when introducing a change to the structure such as exchanging, removing or introducing a new component.

1.5.2. Energy calculation and structure optimization

There are two primary types of calculation methods used in computational chemistry: quantum- and molecular-mechanics. As this system is dealing with non-relativistic (low velocity, $< c/3$) particles, the quantum-mechanical calculations solves the potential energy surface (PES) of the molecule using the Schrödinger equation.^[53] For the molecular-mechanical calculation, Newton's equation is used instead to obtain the energy.

Obtaining an optimized structure of a molecule as well as its' energy is both time-consuming and computationally expensive (in terms of computational resources); this is due to the program not only solving the Schrödinger equation for every atom present, to obtain the energy, but also takes in to account non-bonding interaction with other atoms, *et cetera* with many iterations to find the optimized structure.^[53] For this reason, calculations are often done on a small set (or region) of a molecule if possible; hence why, in this thesis, most of the quantum-mechanical calculations were done using a disaccharide model rather than an oligosaccharide.

A PES map of the electronic structure for a molecule can provide structural information such as the preferable torsional (dihedral) angles, primarily phi ($\phi = \text{H1-C1-O}'_x\text{-C}'_x$) and psi ($\psi = \text{C1-O}'_x\text{-C}'_x\text{-H}'_x$), of a glycosidic link in a specific molecule. This is done by performing an energy calculation for each combination of ϕ and ψ angles from $0^\circ - 360^\circ$ with a specific interval; the resulting energy map will show the preference of the torsional angle by observing the torsional regions which have low energies.

Unlike the quantum-mechanical calculation, molecular-mechanics (also known as classical mechanics) obtains the energy of the molecule using a function which relates both to the coordinates of the atom as well as parameters of the atoms present through a force field.^[53] Rather than calculate all the factors which influences the energy of the molecule for each iteration, as done for the quantum-mechanical calculations, a force field is used; where the energy of the system is defined based on the atoms and their atom type involved (ex: sp^3 vs sp^2 C, C in carbonyls, N in amides, etc.), as an energy function which is required for: stretching a bond between two atoms, bending for an angle between three atoms, rotation around a bond which involves four atoms, van der-Waals interaction, electrostatic interaction and non-bonding interactions.^[53]

As the energy is a function of defined parameters, the molecular-mechanics calculations are faster than quantum-mechanics calculation; this method is used when looking at the macromolecular structure where the preciseness of the energy calculated of the molecule is not as important as observing other information which could be obtained, such as the conformation of an oligosaccharide over time.^[53]

1.5.3. Conformational analysis

The conformation of the carbohydrate, more specifically the ring puckering, can be obtained by running a program, such as the CPPTRAJ^[54] module of the Amber^[55] software package, which calculates, for a pyranose ring, the spherical coordinates (q_2, φ_2, q_3), using the Cremer-Pople^[56] method, which is defined as:

If $N > 3$ and N is an odd number (such as a furanose):

$$m = 2, 3 \dots \frac{N-1}{2}$$

$$q_m \cos \varphi_m = \sqrt{2/N} \sum_{j=1}^N z_j \cos \left[\frac{2\pi m(j-1)}{N} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$q_m \sin \varphi_m = -\sqrt{2/N} \sum_{j=1}^N z_j \sin \left[\frac{2\pi m(j-1)}{N} \right] \quad (2)$$

If $N > 3$ and N is an even number (such as a pyranose):

For $m = 2 \dots \frac{N}{2} - 1$: apply equations (1) and (2)

$$q_{N/2} = \sqrt{1/N} \sum_{j=1}^N z_j \cos[\pi(j-1)] = \sqrt{1/N} \sum_{j=1}^N z_j (-1)^{j-1} \quad (3)$$

Where N is the number of atoms in the cyclic ring (6 for a pyranose)^[56]; z is the displacement of the plane with respect to the mean plane being $z = 0$. m is the current puckering coordinate, defined as $m = N - 3$; $m = 2$ is the least possible value possible and a pyranose has only two possible puckering coordinates ($m = 2$ and 3). q_m is the puckering amplitude and φ_m is the phase angle; both furanose and pyranose has one amplitude-phase pair coordinate (q_2, φ_2) and pyranose has an addition puckering coordinate q_3 .^[56]

The pseudorotational phase angle (φ , in $^\circ$) and the magnitude of the distortion of the ring (θ , in $^\circ$) have been defined from the above; the total puckering amplitude (Q , in \AA) and the Cartesian coordinates (q_x, q_y, q_z) can be obtained ^[56, 57]:

$$Q^2 = \sum_m q_m^2 = \sum_{j=1}^N z_j^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} q_2 &= Q \sin \theta \\ q_x &= q_2 \cos \varphi_2 \\ q_y &= q_2 \sin \varphi_2 \\ q_z &= q_3 = Q \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The pyranose conformation can be obtained by plotting a spherical (3D-sphere) graph with spherical coordinates (Q, θ, φ) or (q_2, φ_2, q_3); or with the Cartesian coordinates (q_x, q_y, q_z). ^[56, 57] The conformation could be plotted on a 2D-graph by plotting (φ, θ)^[57] as seen in Figure 18; this is best displayed using a map projection including the “fish eye” Hammer-Aitoff^[58] projection and the rectangular Mercator^[59] projection.

Figure 18. The spherical coordinates of the Cremer-Pople puckering coordinates showing the conformation of the pyranose ring. A spherical polar plot using the coordinates (Q, φ, θ) , which is relatable to (q_2, φ_2, q_3) , using the atomic order C1-C2-C3-C4-C5-O5; a Stoddart diagram was used to show the northern & southern hemispheres for clarity of the puckering expected at the Tropic of Cancer ($\theta = 66.5^\circ$) and Tropic of Capricorn ($\theta = 113.5^\circ$).^[56]

The conformation of the carbohydrate can be observed in a 3D model (such as PDB or MOL2) by using the graphical representation PaperChain^[60] in Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD^[61], version 1.9.1; <http://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Research/vmd/>). The colouring of the polyhedral within the cyclic ring based on the puckering amplitude (q_2) calculated which gives similar conformations; such as colouring the polyhedral blue if the sugar is in the boat configuration and will not differentiate the pucker with respect to the orientation of the conformation, whether it be in the ${}^{i,j}B$ or $B_{i,j}$ configuration as long as the q_2 are very close.^[60]

CHAPTER 2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

2.1. Purpose of this research

The number of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms is increasing due to a wide use of antibiotics; this is a major problem as there is a decrease in the effectiveness of commonly-used antibiotics used to treat certain illnesses.^[62-64] Carbohydrate-based vaccines are being looked at as a safe alternative to solve this issue by reducing the opportunity that microorganism have to cause an illness which leads to a decreased use of antibiotics.^[26]

A synthetic multivalent CPS vaccine, one where the vaccine is cross reactive against various CPS of microorganisms in the majority of gastrointestinal-related illnesses, could be developed which will help significantly lower the incidence of antibiotic usage.

2.2. Objectives of this research

The objectives of this research is to isolate and identify the composition of the capsular polysaccharide present on *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 as well as analyze the structural conformation of the capsular polysaccharide of *Clostridium bolteae* strains 16351 and 14578.

2.2.1. Structural characterization of the capsular polysaccharide of *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395

In order to characterize the structure of *C. perfringens* strain 1395's CPS, the identity of the monosaccharide components and their linkages must be identified as well as both the anomeric and absolute configurations for each component.

2.2.2. Conformational analysis of *Clostridium bolteae* strains 16351 and 14578

For the conformational analysis, the preferred torsion angles along the glycosidic bond has to be identified as well as the type of structural conformity the polysaccharide will appear as, such as helix or ribbon-like structure.

2.3. Aim of the research

In order to identify the *C. perfringens* CPS, the polysaccharide must first be isolated and purified. The use of analytical instruments are used to identify the composition of the polysaccharide such as GC-MS and NMR.

For the polysaccharide conformational analysis, a molecular dynamic simulation of the characterized *C. bolteae* CPS is done. The end goal is to compare the theoretical structure of the CPS to structural values obtained experimentally such as by NMR.

CHAPTER 3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1. Structural analysis of *Clostridium perfringens* capsular polysaccharide

3.1.1. Culture acquisition

A human isolate of *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 was obtained through Dr. Mallozzi, University of Arizona. The received samples were then freeze-dried (lyophilized) using Labconco Freezone 12 at 0.030 torr and at -55°C.

3.1.2. Isolation and purification of the capsular polysaccharide

The capsular polysaccharide (CPS) was extracted using a hot water-phenol method, with a 3:2 ratio of water to phenol; this method separates the CPS and lipopolysaccharides into the aqueous layer away from the lipids and proteins content of the cells which remains in the phenol layer.^[65] The extraction was done by dissolving the lyophilized sample in a small aliquot of deionized water where it was transferred to a round-bottom flask and filled with a partial amount of the required water; this initial solution was heated to 70°C in a hot water bath and stirred for one hour in a hot water bath to ensure all the cells were dissolved. After the hour, the remaining volume of water and the phenol were added and this solution was left stirring at 70°C for an additional 6-7 hours followed by cooling the solution overnight on ice. The aqueous layer (the supernatant) was retained and the amount removed was replenished with fresh water for the next extraction for a total of three extractions.

The collected supernatant was dialyzed using a 1 kDa molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) dialysis bag (Spectra/Pro 6 Dialysis Membrane, Spectrum Labs) under running water for 24 hours to remove any traces of phenol and any small cellular content; afterwards, the dialyzed supernatant was then frozen and lyophilized. The lyophilized sample was hydrolyzed with 4.0% acetic acid at 105°C for 3 hours, for purification of the

sample, followed by centrifugation at 5,000 RPM for 10 minutes, extracting the supernatant and using water to replenish the solution for another two extraction. The acid-treated extract was further purified by using size-exclusion chromatography with a Bio-Gel[®] P-2 gel; each fraction collected (~2.0 mL) was frozen then lyophilized and the fraction containing the CPS was used for analysis.

3.1.3. Composition analyses

3.1.3.1. Monosaccharide composition analysis using the alditol acetate (AA) method

To determine what monosaccharides are present in the CPS, the alditol acetate (AA) method is performed which consists of four major steps: hydrolysis, reduction, acetylation and analysis. As carbohydrates are non-volatile due to hydrogen bonding, the products must be chemically converted to volatile compounds for analysis by both GC and GC-MS; this is achieved by acetylation of the hydroxyl group.^[1]

For hydrolyzing the CPS to its monosaccharide constituents, a strong acid is needed; the acid of choice used is trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) which, due to its volatility (boiling point is at 72°C), makes it easy to remove the acid at the end of the hydrolysis step whereas other strong acid would otherwise concentrate in the reduced volume (such as sulfuric acid which has its boiling point at 337°C).^[66] A small amount of the CPS (0.5-1.0 mg) is hydrolyzed with 4 M TFA at 105°C for 4.5 hours followed by evaporation of the solution.^[1]

A small amount of water is then added to hydrolyzed sample and then reduced with a pinch of sodium borodeuteride (NaBD₄), leaving the reaction to occur overnight. This step causes the monosaccharide units present to reduce the aldoses to its open-chain alditol forms, preventing the carbohydrate from going in to the closed-ring forms that would

happen due to equilibrium if the sugar was still in the aldose form. An advantage of using NaBD₄ over sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) is that the reduction of the C1 will add a deuterium, causing an increased mass at one end of the alditol, which is helpful in distinguishing the “top” (C1) and “bottom” (C6) of the alditol when identifying the peaks in a mass spectrum.^[1]

A few drops of glacial acetic acid is added to the sample which stop the NaBD₄ reaction by catalyzing the formation of tetramethyl borate (B(OCH₃)₄) gas. Further removal of the borate compounds was done by dissolving and evaporating the sample three times with a solution containing 5% acetic acid (AcOH) and 95% methanol (MeOH).^[1] Acetic anhydride (AcOAc) was then added to the vial and left to react at 105°C for 2 hours followed by evaporation after cooling the sample. This step acetylates all available hydroxyl groups which makes the resulting product a volatile compound known as an alditol acetate (Scheme 1).^[1] The alditol acetate product is then extracted in to a new vial by dissolving the sample with dichloromethane (DCM, methylene chloride, CH₂Cl₂) and purified by running through a sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄) column; the purified sample was then evaporated to dryness followed by analysis using GC-MS in which the sample was dissolved in DCM prior to injection.^[1, 67-69]

Scheme 1. The alditol acetate method. The polysaccharide is hydrolyzed to a monosaccharide with 4M trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). Reduction with sodium borodeuteride (NaBD_4) keeps the sugar in the aldose form and the acetic anhydride (AcOAc) acetylates the hydroxyl groups.

3.1.3.2. Monosaccharide linkage analysis using the partially methylated alditol acetate (PMAA) method.

The partially methylated alditol acetate (PMAA) method is used to analyze the linkages of the sugars. The purpose of the methylation is to differentiate the initially free hydroxyl groups, now *O*-methyl, from the linked hydroxyl groups which would end up as an *O*-acetylated group through the AA method (Scheme 2).^[1]

First, the sample is treated with 2.2 mL of iodomethane (CH_3I) in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and a pinch of sodium hydroxide ($\text{NaOH}_{(s)}$) and left to react for 4.5

hours to ensure that all the free hydroxyls present are methylated. Purification of the methylated CPS was done by transferring the solution to a glass centrifuge tube and adding an equal amount of water and CH_2Cl_2 (~2 mL).

After mixing, the sample was centrifuged at 5,000 RPM for 10 minutes and the resulting supernatant was discarded and the aqueous layer was replenished with fresh water; the water-DCM purification was performed three times. In the end, the CH_2Cl_2 layer was extracted in to a new vial and evaporated. This purified methylated CPS was then subjected to the AA protocol as mentioned in the monosaccharide composition analysis section (section 3.1.3.1).

Scheme 2. The partially methylated alditol acetate method. An α -D-glucose polymer has its free hydroxyl groups are methylated with iodomethane followed by hydrolysis of the glycosidic bonds with 4M trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), resulting in the sample reduced to its partially methylated monosaccharide form. The sugar is reduced with sodium borodeuteride (NaBD_4) followed by acetylation of the hydroxyl with acetic anhydride.

3.1.3.3. Analytical instruments used

The composition of the polysaccharide was determined using both gas chromatography (GC) and gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The end product injected must be both volatile and heat-stable in order to get results for analysis using both GC and GC-MS.^[4]

Methods using the gas chromatography was done using a Varian 3400 instrument with a 30 m x 0.25 mm DB-17 fused silica column with a film thickness of 0.15 μm . 1 μL of sample was injected for analysis using helium as the gas carrier; the sample was analyzed by using a flame ionization detector (FID) and recorded using the program PeakSimple. The GC method is used to get an accurate ratio of each component present in the sample as each component will rearrange itself to a kinetic product, giving a single peak for each component, and all of the sample will be burned thus the intensity height is relative to the component present.^[70]

Identification of each component is done by comparing the relative retention time of the sample to the library of relative retention times collected in our lab; to ensure that the component is correct, a GC-MS analysis is performed for confirmation using a 70 eV electron impact (EI) ionization method and running on a Thermo Finnigan Polaris Q with an Agilent DB-17 GC column. The mass spectra of each component is unique, like a fingerprint, as the peaks of each component differs in its intensity and the cleavage of the molecule with primary and secondary mass loss due to the fragmentation of the molecule from the radical produced by the EI method (see Scheme 3 and Scheme 4 below).

3.1.3.4. Analysis of the mass fragmentation of the alditol acetate derivatives

The radical cation generated from the EI ionization will fragment to produce more stable molecules; the cleavage of the molecule is favoured to occur near methoxylated carbons with a high preference near vicinal methoxylated carbons.^[1] Acetylated carbons can be fragmented but their occurrences – thus the intensity observed – are low due to the unfavourable electron-withdrawing effect of the carbonyl group.^[1]

After the primary fragmentation of the molecule from the radical ion, additional (secondary) fragmentations may occur; for the AA method, the fragmentation would occur from the loss of acetic acid (-60 m/z), ketene (CH_2CO , -42 m/z) and formaldehyde (-30 m/z). If the molecule has an acetamido group present, such as in an *N*-acetylhexosamine, it is possible to an additional loss of ketene without a loss of acetic acid. For the PMAA method, with the presence of both methylated and acetylated carbons present, additional fragmentation losses are possible with an additional loss due to the formation of methanol (-32 m/z). The losses were calculated both by hand as well as by developing macros in Microsoft Excel[®] using Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) to calculate potential losses from the specified structures as well as to calculate the losses from each potential site for determining how the m/z fragment was formed.

With the preference of the backbone cleavage occurring at the methylated carbons, with a preference to vicinal methylated carbons, the intensity of the fragment peaks can help narrow down the linkage sites in the PMAA method. The reduction with sodium borodeuteride helps with narrowing down the linkage site as the charged fission product which retains the “top” will have a +1 m/z difference then the piece containing the “bottom”.

Scheme 3. Primary fragment losses in an AA and PMAA sample. For PMAA samples, the fragmentation will occur on the C-C backbone where methoxylated are present with preference given to vicinal methoxylated carbons.^[1]

Scheme 4. Secondary fragment losses in an AA and PMAA sample.^[1]

3.1.3.5. Smith degradation (periodate oxidation)

The Smith degradation process uses periodate (IO_4^-) to cleave the carbon bond between vicinal diols, or if the carbons are attached to an oxygen atom adjacent to an amine or carbonyl group, by oxidizing the diols to obtain at least two carbonyl functional groups, typically an aldehyde.^[4, 71] Subsequent treatment with mild acid hydrolysis, after reduction of the carbonyls in to alcohols with sodium borohydride, will result in the loss of the cleaved component. This method can provide structural information such as what components are part of the backbone and the sites where the degraded components were attached.

Scheme 5. Smith degradation (periodate oxidation). (A) A general mechanism of the periodate oxidation method with examples of the oxidized products produced from a (B) 4-linked hexose and a (C) terminal hexose. (D) is a 3-linked hexose which is not susceptible to degradation by periodate oxidation.

3.1.4. Structural analysis by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy

3.1.4.1. Background information

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy is used to obtain information about the structure of the CPS. A one-dimensional (1D) proton (^1H) NMR is first performed as an initial starting point for all other NMR techniques used in the analysis of the CPS and is used to assess the purity of the sample. Some basic information can be obtained such as the presence of acetyl compounds and the number of repeating monosaccharide units present that makes up the polysaccharide and if the configuration the sugars are linked (i.e. in an α or β configuration).^[72, 73]

The anomeric protons, which are deshielded due to the anomeric carbon being attached to two oxygen atoms, have their chemical shift (δ , in ppm) located downfield ($\sim\delta_{\text{H}}$ 4.4 – 5.5 ppm) than the other ring protons (δ_{H} 3.2 – 4.5 ppm).^[74, 75] Furthermore, the two anomeric configuration can be differentiated as the ^1H of the anomeric proton (H1) is in the equatorial position (typically if the carbohydrate is in the α -configuration) is further deshielded due to the anomeric effect, causing the signal shifted further downfield ($\sim\delta_{\text{H}}$ 5.1 – 5.3 ppm) than if the H1 was in the axial position (typically the carbohydrate would be in the β -configuration) ($\sim\delta_{\text{H,eq}}$ 4.3 – 4.8 ppm).^[10, 75, 76] Consequently, as the electron density shifts to the anomeric carbon (C1) – thus increasing the shielding – due to the anomeric effect, it is seen that the ^{13}C chemical shift for C1 is further upfield if the electronegative substituent is located in the axial position ($\sim\delta_{\text{C}}$ 98 – 103 ppm; typically the α -configuration) then if the substituent was in the equatorial position ($\sim\delta_{\text{C}}$ 103 – 106 ppm; typically the β -configuration).^[10, 75, 76] Other regions of interest on the 1D ^1H NMR are the

ring proton (R-CH(OH)-R') regions (δ_{H} 3.2 – 4.5 ppm), the methyl on the acetyl group (δ_{H} 1.8 – 2.2 ppm) and methyl peaks (δ_{H} 1.1 – 1.3 ppm).^[75]

The number of monosaccharides that composes the repeating units of the capsular polysaccharide can be inferred by the number of anomeric protons observed; however, some of the signals can be hidden by being overlapped by other signals such as other anomeric peaks and both the large amount of partially- and small amount of non-deuteriated water peaks (HOD and H₂O respectively) which has a chemical shift of $\delta_{\text{H}} \sim 4.8$ ppm at 295 K which can overlap some β -anomeric peaks.^[75, 77] To obtain precisely the number of anomeric peaks present, the employment 2D NMR technique HSQC is recommended or a 1D ¹H NMR at a different temperature to shift the solvent peak.

Various two-dimensional NMR methods are employed to help identify the peaks in the one-dimensional NMR with the results from the sugar composition and linkage analysis. The chemical shift of each proton in the ring based on the proton relationship with other protons can be determined using the 2D correlation spectroscopy (¹H-¹H COSY); the chemical shift of the carbon where the proton is attached can be determined using the proton – carbon heteronuclear single quantum correlation spectroscopy (¹H-¹³C HSQC) is done to find the protons and carbons related to each anomeric peak.^[72, 73]

The technique proton – carbon heteronuclear multiple bond correlation spectroscopy (¹H - ¹³C HMBC) is used to find the relationship between the carbon and a proton located multiple bonds away; this identifies carbons with distinct chemical shifts in aid of their identification such as a confirmation of the number of anomeric peaks and the carbon attached to the amide group in *N*-acetyl compound which has a higher carbon chemical shift.^[72, 73]

In order to assign the peaks to the monosaccharide based on the linkages, aside from using HMBC, two techniques are employed together: the nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy (NOESY) and the total correlation spectroscopy (TOCSY).^[75] Both can be done as either a 2D technique or a selective 1D technique where a peak can be selectively irradiated to gain information relating to that peak. NOESY is used to determine the protons nearest the selected peak through space (within 5 Å) and TOCSY determines the protons present in the spin system of the irradiated peak; TOCSY is used to eliminate the internal ring protons encountered in the NOESY results to find the protons which are not part of the irradiated peak's spin system such as the proton on the other side of the linked saccharide.^[72]

3.1.4.2. Deuterium exchange

A deuterium exchange is often performed to decrease the number of signals/peaks observed; this occurs due to the proton present in the hydroxyl, amine and other functional group rapidly exchanging its proton with the deuterium present in the deuteriated solvent. The side effect of this exchange is that the solvent now becomes partially deuteriated (and, more importantly, partially protonated) which causes the solvent to appear in the ¹H NMR spectrum.^[75]

In order to decrease the signals from the exchangeable protons, several deuterium exchanges must be performed. One method is to freeze-dry (lyophilize) the sample using deuteriated water (D₂O), a commonly used solvent. Each time the sample is lyophilized using D₂O, there are less available protons present on the hydroxyl and other exchanging functional groups as the partially-protonated solvent (in this case HOD and a minor amount of H₂O) is sublimated. As a consequence, when more deuteriated solvent is used, there are

less protons present in the sample causing a decreased proton signal from the deuterium-exchanged functional groups; in addition, with less protons available for exchanging, the less broad the HOD peak will appear in the ^1H NMR.

3.1.4.3. Sample preparation and instrumental information

Samples for NMR analysis were prepared by performing a D_2O exchange by adding 5 drops of deuterium oxide (D_2O) to 2.12 mg of the lyophilized acid-treated CPS, freezing the sample on dry-ice for 10 min followed by lyophilization of the sample; this was repeated for a total of three times. Samples were placed in a WILMAD® NMR tube (Sigma-Aldrich Canada Ltd.) after mixing the sample with 592 μL of D_2O .

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy was used to help determine the structure of the polysaccharide through the information obtained from 1D and 2D NMR techniques. Through the University of Guelph NMR Center, Bruker AVANCE III 400 and 600 MHz NMR spectrometers, the latter equipped with a cryoprobe, were used. The 400 MHz was used for the one-dimensional ^1H NMR spectrum for purification determination whereas the 600 MHz was used for selective 1D techniques and various two-dimensional techniques at 295 K and 326 K. Analysis of the NMR data was done using Bruker Topspin software versions 2.1 and 3.1.

3.2. Computational modelling of *Clostridium bolteae* capsular polysaccharide

3.2.1. Quantum-mechanical calculations and optimization of the molecular structures

Gaussian 2009^[78] was used for both quantum-mechanical calculations and optimization of structures. The dihedral angles (torsion angles) along the glycosidic bond are defined as phi, $\phi(i) = \text{H1}(i)\text{-C1}(i)\text{-OX}(i-1)\text{-CX}(i-1)$, and psi, $\psi(i) = \text{C1}(i)\text{-OX}(i-1)\text{-}$

CX(*i*-1)-HX(*i*-1), where *i* is the current residue and X is the linkage site of *i* to the previous residue (*i*-1).^[79] The exocyclic torsion along the C5-C6 plane, defined as χ^5 (χ^5) = C4-C5-C6-O6, can provide the conformation of the position of the 6th hydroxyl group (O6) is positioned as either *gauche-trans* (*gt*), *gauche-gauche* (*gg*) or *trans-gauche* (*tg*), with respect to the atoms O5 and C4, and is used as a means to quantify the population the preferred conformation at the C5-C6 bond (Figure 19).^[10, 79]

Figure 19. The exocyclic hydroxyl conformations. The conformation of O6, with respect to O5 and C4, is defined as either being *trans-gauche* (*tg*), *gauche-gauche* (*gg*) or *gauche-trans* (*gt*). The exocyclic torsion angle χ^5 (C4-C5-C6-O6), with the torsion angle ranging from -180° to $+180^\circ$ and the respective 0° - 360° in the parenthesis, is defined as follows with a range of $\pm 120^\circ$: χ^5 (*tg*) = -60° (120°), χ^5 (*gg*) = $+60^\circ$ (240°) and χ^5 (*gt*) = $\pm 180^\circ$ ($0^\circ/360^\circ$).

A potential energy surface (PES) scan of the dihedral angles was performed for both the capsular polysaccharide of *C. bolteae* strain 16351^[12] and a structural analog where the D-rhamnose unit is replaced with the opposite absolute configuration L-rhamnose. This was done by modelling four sets of disaccharide units of the CPS, with the mannose in the *gg* exocyclic conformation; where the link sites not involved in the glycosidic bond are methylated rather than remaining as free hydroxyls (**aDm-bDr**: 3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-Rhap-OMe; **bDr-aDm**: 4-OMe- β -D-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe; **aDm-bLr**:

3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -L-Rhap-OMe; and **bLr-aDm**: 4-OMe- β -L-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe).

In addition to the PES of the *C. bolteae* CPS, the PES for the CPS anomer was done where both sugars have the opposite anomeric configuration (**bDm-aDr**: 3-OMe- β -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap-OMe; **aDr-bDm**: 4-OMe- α -D-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-Manp-OMe). Finally, a PES of a disaccharide set composed of α -D-mannose and α -L-rhamnose as they are the major conformation of mannose and rhamnose, respectively, in water^[80] (**aDm-aLr**: 3-OMe- α -D-Manp-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-Rhap-OMe; **aLr-aDm**: 4-OMe- α -L-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe).

Figure 20. The dihedral angles modified to obtain a potential energy surface. The subscript of the torsion angle denotes the residue where the glycosidic bond starts. The torsion angles of the (A) methyl 4-*O*-(3-*O*-methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- β -D-rhamnopyranoside, aDm-bDr, is defined as $\phi_M = \text{H1-C1-O4'-C4'}$, $\psi_M = \text{C1-O4'-C4'-H4'}$ and $\chi^5 = \text{C4-C5-C6-O6}$. (B) Methyl 3-*O*-(4-*O*-methyl- β -D-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside, bDr-aDm, has the torsion angles defined as $\phi_R = \text{H1-C1-O3'-C3'}$ and $\psi_R = \text{C1-O3'-C3'-H3'}$.

The *ab initio* calculation method chosen for the PES was the Hartree-Fock (HF) with the basis set 6-31G(d) with no implicit solvent. The relaxed scan, which optimizes the structure after each change in the parameters, was initiated by using the keyword **opt=ModRedundant; NoSymm** was used to prevent Gaussian from terminating during the calculation when the point group of the molecule changes. The redundant coordinate editor was used to increase both the ϕ and ψ torsion angles by 30° with 11 steps using setting the 'scan coordinate'; in addition, the following dihedral angles were frozen to the specified value to reduce intra-molecular hydrogen bonding to decrease an artificial change in the energy (though it was impossible to completely avoid this): χ^2 (H2-C2-O2-HO2) for both mannose and rhamnose were set to -30° ; the χ^3 (H3-C3-O3-HO3) of the rhamnose residue was constrained to $+60^\circ$ and the χ^4 (H4-C4-O4-HO4) of the mannose residue was frozen at 180° .

3.2.2. Molecular dynamic simulation

The molecular dynamic (MD) simulations were performed using the AMBER 10^[55] software package with Amber Tools 14^[81] and the GLYCAM^[82] (version 06_j-1) force field. Parameters for the molecular dynamic simulation was adapted from Dr. Richards.^[83]

A trisaccharide unit, α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp, was subjected to a 50 ns MD simulation with an implicit water solvent model using the generalized Born solvation model. The system was first minimized using 250 steps of steepest decent followed by 250 steps of conjugate gradient minimization. The system was then equilibrated from 5 K to 310 K over 25 ps. Afterwards, the simulation was started with a 1 fs timestep with NPT conditions at 1 atm and 310 K; the temperature was maintained using

the Berendsen^[84] thermostat with the velocity being rescaled every 1 ps. The external dielectric constant was left as the default value of 78.5 and the bond length was constrained for all bonds containing hydrogen by using the SHAKE^[85] algorithm.

For the explicit solvation MD simulation, a decarepeat unit of the CPS, $[\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\alpha\text{-D-Manp}(1\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\beta\text{-D-Rhap}(1\rightarrow)]_{10}$, as well as a model of the most abundant configuration, $[\rightarrow 3)\text{-}\alpha\text{-D-Manp}(1\rightarrow 4)\text{-}\alpha\text{-L-Rhap}(1\rightarrow)]_{10}$, was used with the reducing end capped with a hydroxyl group. A periodic box with 5,833 TIP3P^[86] water molecules was used as the explicit solvent; the dimension of this solvate box was 18.774 Å X 18.774 Å X 18.774 Å. Prior to the start of the dynamic simulation, the system was relaxed to remove any high energy contacts of the water molecules with the CPS using 500 steps of steepest descent followed by 500 conjugate gradient minimization with the oligosaccharide being held using a 500.0 kcal/mol·Å² restraint; afterwards, the system was minimized using 1000 steps of steepest descent followed by 1500 conjugate gradient with no restraints.

After minimization of the system, a simulated annealing was done by changing the temperature from 0 K to 295 K over 50 ps, back to 0 K in 50 ns and a slower increase back to 295 K over 100 ps; the system was equilibrated at 295 K for an additional 100 ps prior to the start of the MD simulation. The temperature was regulated using Langevin^[87] thermostat with the collision frequency (γ) set to 1 ps⁻¹ for the annealing and equilibrium.

The 5 ns explicit TIP3P^[86] solvent MD simulation was performed with a 2 fs timestep with NTP conditions at 1 atm and 295 K; the temperature was maintained using the Langevin^[87] thermostat with the collision frequency (γ) set to 2 ps⁻¹. All bonds containing hydrogen were constrained using the SHAKE^[85] algorithm;. The non-bonding interaction was set to 8 Å and the electrostatic interaction was left unscaled.

The module CPPTRAJ^[54] was used, upon completion of the MD simulation, to obtain the ensemble trajectory files, torsion angles of specified atoms and residues, and Cremer-Pople ring puckering values for the pyranose structures. The program VMD was used to visualize the resulting MD trajectory ensemble.

The statistical program R^[88] (version 3.1.2; <http://www.R-project.org/>) was used for processing statistical information such as the torsion angles and puckering coordinates over time. The R package ‘fields’^[89] was used to display the occurrence of the phi and psi torsion angles; for plotting the Cremer-Pople puckering coordinates, the R packages ‘sphereplot’^[90] and ‘rgl’^[91] were used; the Hammer-Aitoff projection was performed using the R script from the “allsky projections in R” project by Observatório do Valongo – UFRJ.^[92]

Displaying the 3D structures in this PDF document was possible by rendering an Wavefront OBJ file, using VMD for molecules and both R & Blender[®] (version 2.74r2; <http://www.blender.org>) for the spherical objects, which was then imported in to MeshLab^[93] (version 1.3.4β, <http://meshlab.sourceforge.net/>) where the file was converted to a Universal 3D (U3D) file that was then embedded in to the document using Adobe Acrobat X (version 10.7.1, <http://www.adobe.com/>). To view the 3D structures (Figure 79 and Figure 85), ensure that this PDF document is open in Adobe Acrobat X (or Adobe Reader X) or their later version, and click on to the 3D icon ; to end the 3D view, right click the figure and select ‘disable content’. For best results, please ensure that the double-side rendering is enabled in the ‘3D & Multimedia’ section in the preference option.

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF *CLOSTRIDIUM PERFRINGENS* CAPSULAR POLYSACCHARIDE

4.1. Carbohydrate composition of the capsular polysaccharide

The purified CPS was chemically modified using the alditol acetate (AA) method; based on the relative retention time (Figure 21) and the fragmentation pattern observed, the CPS was determined to be composed with mannose (Man), galactose (Gal) and 2-acetamido-2-deoxy-galactosamine (*N*-acetyl galactosamine, GalNAc).

Figure 21. The GC-MS elution profile of the carbohydrate composition of the alditol acetate derivative CPS with the components identified by their relative retention time and fragmentation pattern by the mass spectra with the GC-MS.

Table 1. The retention time, percent area and the relative ratio of the monosaccharides obtained by using Gas Chromatography with a Flame Ionization Detector. The ratio is relative to the area of the mannose component.

Component	GC-MS Retention Time (min)	GC-FID Retention Time (min)	% Area	Relative Ratio
Mannose	36.53	59.15	17.41	1.00
Glucose	37.14	60.67	49.66	2.85
Galactose	37.53	61.10	24.00	1.38
<i>N</i> -acetyl galactosamine	52.62	88.28	8.93	0.51

The mass spectra of the hexoses (Figure 22 - Figure 24) have the same fragmentation masses, caused by both primary and secondary fragmentation losses, but differ from each other, in both the intensity of some of the peaks as well as the retention time, due to the different position of the hydroxyl groups. The characteristic intense fragmentation peaks of the hexoses includes m/z 43, 128, 139, 140, 187, 188, 259 and 260 (Table 2).

Table 2. High intensity fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the hexoses Man, Glc and Gal. The difference in the +1 m/z is due to the presence of deuterium on the “top” end of the carbohydrate. The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
43	N/A (Acetyl cation)	N/A
128	290	-2(60), -42
139 / 140	361 / 362	-3(60), -42
187 / 188	289 / 290	-60, -42
259 / 260	361 / 362	-60, -42

Figure 22. Electron-impact mass spectrum of the component mannose

Figure 23. Electron-impact mass spectrum of the component glucose

Figure 24. Electron-impact mass spectrum of the component galactose

Figure 25. Electron-impact mass spectrum of the component *N*-acetyl galactosamine

The *N*-acetyl galactosamine eluted as a broad peak, appearing as positively skewed peak in the GC elution profile. Several characteristic fragmentation peaks for the *N*-acetyl hexosamine includes *m/z* 43, 85, 97, 259 and 318 (Table 3). The loss of ketene (-42 *m/z*) from *m/z* 360 without any acetic acid (-60 *m/z*) formation is possible due to the acetamido group of the *N*-acetyl galactosamine.

Table 3. High intensity fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the *N*-acetyl galactosamine. The loss of fragment *m/z* 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of *m/z* 42 is due to the formation of ketene.

Peak (<i>m/z</i>)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
43	N/A (Acetyl cation)	N/A
85	145	-60
97	217	-2(60)
	360	-3(60), -2(42)
138 / 139	360 / 361	-3(60), -42
156	360	-2(60), -2(42)
198/199	360 / 361	-2(60), -42
240	360	-2(60)
258/259	360 / 361	-60, -42
318	360	-42

4.2. Sugar linkage analysis of the capsular polysaccharide

The CPS was modified using the partially methylated alditol acetate (PMAA) method. Unlike the compositional analysis, the linkage analysis is more complex and requires the EI mass spectra are required for proper determination.

Based on the retention time and the mass fragmentation pattern of each component the linkage analysis (Figure 26) showed the presence of terminal and 4-linked glucose, 3-linked galactose, (2,3)-linked mannose and galactose, and a 4-linked *N*-acetyl galactosamine.

Figure 26. The GC elution profile of the linkage analysis.

Table 4. The retention time, percent area and the relative ratio & intensity of the PMAA result obtained by using Gas Chromatography with a Flame Ionization Detector.

Component	GC-MS Retention Time (min)	GC-FID Retention Time (min)	% Area	Relative Ratio	Relative Intensity
Glc (1→)	36.45	39.52	31.23	9.81	1.00
→ 4) Glc (1→)	41.35	45.92	19.45	6.11	0.62
→ 3) Gal (1→)	42.23	46.63	11.16	3.51	0.36
→ 2,3) Man (1→)	45.47	49.63	17.75	5.58	0.57
→ 2,3) Gal (1→)	46.26	50.28	17.22	5.41	0.55
→ 4) GalNAc (1→)	72.20	68.23	3.18	1.00	0.10

The terminal hexose, determined to be a glucose by comparing the retention time of 36.45 min to the retention time of a standard PMAA Glc done previously in the lab on the GC-MS, had the greatest intensity peak in the GC elution profile and is used as the base time for obtaining the relative retention time of all other peaks. The fragmentation pattern indicates that the glucose is in a pyranose form, linked only at the 1st and 5th position, which allowed methylation at the other hydroxyl position; more specifically, due to the presence of the methoxy group at C4, there were many intense peaks present from the fragmentation between C3-C4 such as m/z 102, 129, 161 and 162 (Figure 27).

Table 5. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 36.45 min (terminal hexose). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene. The loss of fragment m/z 32 is due to the formation of the stable product methanol.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
86	118	-32
87	161	-32, -42
102	162	-60
129	161	-32
145	205	-60
161	C4 – C6	Fragment between C3-C4
205	C3 – C6	Fragment between C2-C3

Figure 27. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the terminal glucose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose, at the retention time of 36.45 min in the GC-MS. The primary fragmented molecules were formed through the loss of the stable products acetic acid (m/z 60) and methanol (m/z 32); the secondary fragment losses are from formaldehyde (m/z 30) and ketene (m/z 42).

Figure 28. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 4-linked glucose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,4,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 4-linked hexose, at the retention time of 41.35 min in the GC-MS.

The peak with the retention time of 41.35 min on the GC-MS was determined to be a 4-linked hexose with the characteristic peaks m/z: 99, 113, 118, 131 and 173 (Figure 28). Based on the relative retention time to the terminal glucose, it was determined this is a 4-linked glucose by comparing the relative retention time to an internal list of PMAA relative times collected in our lab.

Table 6. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 41.35 min (4-linked hexose). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene. The loss of fragment m/z 32 is due to the formation of the stable product methanol and the loss of m/z 30 is due to the formation of formaldehyde.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
71	233	-2(60), -42
87	189	-60, -42
99	189 233	-60, -30 -60, -32, -42
102	162	-60
113	233	-2(60)
118	C1 – C2	Fragment between C2-C3
131	233	-60, -42
173	233	-60

The peak with the retention time of 42.23 minutes on the GC-MS was found to be a 3-linked hexose based on the characteristic peaks m/z : 87, 118, 129, 143, 160 and 161 (Figure 29). By comparison of the relative retention time to the list of relative retention time collected in the lab, this peak was found to be a 3-linked galactose.

As the methoxy group alternates with the acetyl group along the 3-linked hexitol, many more m/z peaks are observed in the EI mass spectrum, unlike those derived from compounds with vicinal methoxy groups such as the terminal hexose, due to no particularly preferred fragmentation sites being available.

Figure 29. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 3-linked galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,3,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 3-linked hexose, at the retention time of 42.23 min in the GC-MS.

Table 7. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 42.23 min (3-linked hexose). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene. The loss of fragment m/z 32 is due to the formation of the stable product methanol and the loss of m/z 30 is due to the formation of formaldehyde.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
86	118 234	-32 -2(32), -2(42)
87	161	-32, -42
99	161 233	-32, -30 -60, -32, -42
101	161 277	-60 -60, -32, -2(42)
118	C1 – C2	Fragment between C2-C3
128	190 234	-32, -30 -2(32), -42
129	161 277	-32 -2(32), -2(42)
143	233 277	-60, -30 -60, -32, -42
160	234	-32, -42
161	C4 – C6	Fragment between C3-C4
202	234	-32
203	277	-32, -42
217	277	-60
245	277	-32

A 2,3-linked hexose had eluted with the retention time of 45.47 minutes on the GC-MS. Unlike the other peaks which were identified by their relative retention times to previously identified peaks in the lab, there was no existing entry for this retention time. Based on the fragmentation pattern and the characteristic peaks m/z : 86, 129, 161, 202 and 262; it was assumed that this is a 2,3-linked hexose.

The fragmentation pattern observed at 45.47 minutes the same pattern as the peak at 46.26 minutes, which the latter was determined to be a 2,3-linked galactose based on previous lab data. The fragmentation pattern, although the same with 45.47 minutes, differed by different intensities for m/z : 86-87, 100, 161 and 262 (Figure 30). By eliminating all the peaks identified at the end, and with the use of NMR, it was found that the peak at 45.47 minutes is a 2,3-linked mannose.

Figure 30. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 2,3-linked mannose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,3,5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-4,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 2,3-linked hexose, at the retention time of 45.47 min in the GC-MS.

Table 8. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 45.47 and 46.26 min (2,3-linked hexoses). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene. The loss of fragment m/z 32 is due to the formation of the stable product methanol and the loss of m/z 30 is due to the formation of formaldehyde.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
86	146 262	-60 -60, -32, -2(42)
87	161	-32, -42
100	262	-2(60), -42
128	218 262	-60, -30 -60, -32, -42
129	161	-32
161	C4 – C6	Fragment between C3-C4
188	262	-32, -42
202	262	-60
262	C1 – C4	Fragment between C4-C5

Figure 31. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 2,3-linked galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,3,5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-4,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 2,3-linked hexose, at the retention time of 46.26 min in the GC-MS.

A broad peak eluted at 72.20 minutes on the GC-MS was determined to be a 4-linked *N*-acetyl galactosamine by the characteristic peak, for the linkage, with: m/z 173, 233 and a minor peak at 203; characteristic peaks for the presence of a methylated *N*-acetyl group are m/z 75, 99, 117 and 159 (Figure 32).

Table 9. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 72.20 min (4-linked *N*-acetylhexosamine). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid, the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene and the loss of m/z 30 is due to the formation of formaldehyde.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
75	159	-2(42)
99	159 189	-60 -60, -30
117	159	-42
159	C1 – C2	Fragment between C2-C3
173	233	-60
203	C1 – C3	Fragment between C3-C4
233	C3 – C6	Fragment between C2-C3

Figure 32. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 4-linked *N*-acetylgalactosamine. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,4,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-(2-*N*-methylacetamide)-3,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 4-linked *N*-acetylhexosamine, at the retention time of 72.20 min in the GC-MS.

4.3. Smith degradation (periodate oxidation) analysis

The Smith degradation method uses periodate oxidation to cleave between vicinal diols that are present. With the sugar composition analysis method (AA), it was observed that nearly all the glucose units were destroyed and that the galactose component still remained higher than the mannose component (Figure 33).

By using the sugar linkage analysis method (PMAA), the intact components were: a terminal glucose; a terminal, 2-linked and 3-linked galactose; 3-linked mannose; 4-linked GalNAc; and traces of the 2,3-linked mannose and galactose (Figure 34). There was presence of 4-linked glucose but it was considered that this was due to not enough periodate present to degrade the remainder of this sugar as this component is susceptible to periodate degradation.

By taking the area of the identified peaks seen in the non-oxidized samples and adjusting the intensity to match the % area of the 4-linked *N*-acetylgalactosamine, which is resistant to the degradation, the degraded sample accounts for 60.78% of the total area of the identified peaks in the non-oxidized sample (Table 13); however, the adjusted area values may be off as the GalNAc peak was broad.

Table 10. The retention time, percent area and the relative ratio & intensity of the sugar composition analysis (AA) of the Smith-degraded CPS result obtained by using Gas Chromatography with a Flame Ionization Detector. The relative ratio is based on the least area occupied whereas the relative intensity is based to the maximum area observed.

Component	GC-FID Ret. Time (min)	% Area	Relative Ratio	Relative Intensity
Mannose (Man)	59.70	12.69	1.45	0.38
Glucose (Glc)	60.78	5.24	0.60	0.16
Galactose (Gal)	61.41	33.02	3.77	1.00
<i>N</i> -acetyl galactosamine (GalNAC)	90.00	8.75	1.00	0.26

Table 11. The retention time, percent area and the relative ratio & intensity of the linkage analysis (PMAA) of the Smith-degraded CPS result obtained by using Gas Chromatography with a Flame Ionization Detector.

Component	GC-MS Retention Time (min)	GC-FID Ret. Time (min)	% Area	Relative Ratio	Relative Intensity
Glc (1 →	36.47	39.52	8.54	4.84	0.38
Gal (1→	37.68	41.10	12.46	7.06	0.56
→ 4) Glc (1 →	41.36	46.00	22.44	12.72	1.00
→ 2) Man (1 →	40.24	44.52	6.47	3.67	0.29
→ 3) Man (1 →	41.73	46.20	20.26	11.48	0.90
→ 2,3) Man (1 →	45.49	49.07	1.76	1.00	0.07
→ 2) Gal (1 →	41.92	46.38	8.46	4.79	0.38
→ 3) Gal (1 →	42.26	46.70	13.90	7.88	0.62
→ 2,3) Gal (1 →	46.27	50.22	2.38	1.35	0.10
→ 4) GalNAc (1 →	72.46	68.57	3.59	2.03	0.16

Table 12. Comparison of the sugar composition analysis (AA) of the non-oxidized (intact) and oxidized (Smith degraded) samples obtained by using Gas Chromatography with a Flame Ionization Detector. The relative ratios are based on the area of the mannose component of the respective treatment. The value of the oxidized relative ratio was also adjusted to keep the GalNAc ratio of both samples the same for a baseline.

Component	% Area Non-oxidized	% Area Oxidized	Rel. Ratio Non-oxidized	Rel. Ratio Oxidized (adjusted)
Mannose	17.41	12.69	1.00	1.00 (0.74)
Glucose	49.66	5.24	2.85	0.41 (0.31)
Galactose	24.00	33.02	1.38	2.60 (1.94)
<i>N</i> -acetyl galactosamine	8.93	8.75	0.51	0.69 (0.51)
Total % area	100.00	59.69		

Table 13. Comparison of the sugar linkage analysis (PMAA) of the non-oxidized (intact) and oxidized (Smith degraded) samples obtained by using Gas Chromatography.

Non-oxidized Component ^a	% Area	Hexose % Area ^b	Oxidized Component ^a	Adjusted ^c % Area	Hexose % Area ^b
T-Glc	31.23	50.68	T-Glc	7.57	7.57
4-Glc	19.45		4-Glc	(19.90) ^d	(27.48) ^d
		28.38	T-Gal	11.05	32.85
			2-Gal	7.50	
3-Gal	11.16		3-Gal	12.33	
2,3-Gal	17.22		2,3-Gal	1.97	
		17.75	2-Man	5.74	24.75
			3-Man	17.96	
2,3-Man	17.75		2,3-Man	1.05	
4-GalNAc	3.18	3.18	4-GalNAc	3.18	3.18
Total % Area		100			60.78 (88.26)^d

(a) The component listing has been shortened for spacing; the T- stands for terminal. (b) This is the sum of the % area for that sugar component. (c) Adjusted so the % area of the 4-GalNAc (degradation resistant) in both samples are the same amount. (d) The 4-Glc values are in parenthesis as this component should not have been present after degradation due to not enough periodate used.

Figure 33. The GC-FID elution profile of the sugar composition analysis (AA) of the Smith-degraded capsular polysaccharide sample.

Figure 34. The GC-FID elution profile of the sugar linkage analysis (PMAA) of the Smith-degraded capsular polysaccharide.

The fragmentation pattern of the terminal glucose, eluted at 36.47 minutes on the GC-MS, has the same pattern and peak intensity as seen in the linkage analysis of the non-oxidized CPS (Figure 35). The fragmentation pattern of the terminal galactose with a retention time of 37.68 minutes had the same fragment peaks but significantly differed in the intensities of the peaks m/z 102 and 129, which were less intense, and a smaller difference noted in the intensity of the m/z 205 peak being slightly less than m/z 161 for the terminal galactose compared to the terminal glucose (Figure 27, Figure 36).

The presence of the 4-linked glucose (retention time 41.36 minutes), and in such high abundance and based on the adjusted % area of the 4-linked glucose of the oxidized sample compared to the unoxidized sample, it is likely not enough sodium periodate was used as this component should have been degraded due to the presence of the vicinal hydroxyls (positions 2 and 3). The fragmentation pattern of the 4-linked glucose matches the observed fragmentation pattern from the non-oxidized CPS (Figure 28, Figure 37).

The 3-linked galactose (retention time 42.26 minutes) is resistant to periodate oxidation due to no presence of vicinal diols; as such, it is unsurprising that the adjusted % area of the 3-linked galactose is nearly the same before and after the oxidation method. The presence of some extra 3-linked galactose is due to the breaking of the O2-linked sugar in the 2,3-linked galactose; this is discussed further in the next paragraph. The mass spectrum of the 3-linked galactose is identical to the one observed earlier in the non-oxidized sample (Figure 29, Figure 39).

The majority of the 2,3-linked galactose (retention time 46.27 minutes) was broken into three components: terminal galactose, 2-linked galactose and a small amount into 3-linked galactose. This link break occurs when the connecting sugars are susceptible to the

degradation process and lost after hydrolyzed by a mild acid treatment performed post degradation. The fragmentation pattern of the small remenant of the 2,3-linked galactose appeared exactly the same as the one seen in the non-oxidized sample (Figure 31, Figure 40). As the 2-linked galactose was in high amounts, it is susceped that a terminal glucose was present on the 3-linked site of the 2,3-linked galactose.

The terminal galactose, found at the retention time of 37.68 minutes, has the same fragmented pattern seen in the terminal glucose but differs by having a lower peak intensity of the peak m/z 102. The 2-linked galactose, with the retention time of 41.92 min, has the characteristic fragmentation peaks m/z : 129, 130, 161, 190, 202 and 234; the peaks m/z 161 and 190 are important as they appear in fragmentation pattern of 2-linked hexoses due to the presense of vicinal di-*O*-methyls at the C3 & C4 position which is the preferred site of fragmentation (Figure 38).

Table 14. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 41.92 min (2-linked hexose). The loss of fragment peaks is due to the formation of: acetic acid (-60), ketene (-42) and methanol (-32).

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
87	161	-32, -42
129	161	-32
130	190	-60
145	205	-60
161	C4 – C6	Fragment between C3-C4
190	C1 – C3	Fragment between C3-C4
202	234	-32
234	C1 – C4	Fragment between C4-C5

The 2,3-linked mannose (retention time 45.49 min) also had its linkages broken, resulting in a majority of 3-linked mannose, minor amount of 2-linked mannose and a trace of the remaining 2,3-linked mannose. The mass spectrum of the remaining 2,3-linked mannose is nearly identical to the spectrum observed in the non-oxidized sample; however, two new peaks, m/z 118 and 143, were observed of relatively high intensity that indicates that there may be more than one component present at the same retention time such as 3,4-linked glucose which appears to have the same relative retention time based on previous lab results indicating that the presence of 2,3-linked mannose is even lower than expected (Figure 30, Figure 43). As the 3-linked site is at a higher intensity, it is suspected that there is a terminal glucose present on the 2-linked site of the 2,3-linked mannose. The minor amount of 2-linked mannose, which eluted at 40.24 minutes, had the characteristic peaks m/z : 84, 88, 129, 130, 145, 161 and 190 (Figure 41). Unlike the 2-linked galactose (Figure 38), the 2-linked mannose had less peaks present but with higher intensity, especially the peaks at the vicinal di-*O*-methyls m/z 161 and 190. As there was relatively little presence of the 2-linked mannose compared to the 3-linked mannose, and no terminal mannose seen, it can be assumed that the carbohydrate linked at O2 is resistant to the periodate oxidation.

Table 15. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 41.92 min (2-linked hexose). The loss of fragment peaks is due to the formation of: acetic acid (-60), ketene (-42) and methanol (-32).

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
87	161	-32, -42
88	190	-60, -42
129	161	-32
130	190	-60
145	205	-60
161 / 190	C4 – C6 / C1 – C3	Fragment between C3-C4

The 3-linked mannose eluted at 41.73 minutes and had the characteristic peaks m/z: 87, 118, 129, 143, 161, 202 and 234 (Figure 42). The fragmentation pattern was similar to that of 3-linked galactose (Figure 39) but had a lower peak intensity for m/z 118 and 160 and a higher intense m/z: 100, 202 and 234.

Table 16. Intense characteristic fragments observed in the EI mass spectra of the peak eluted at 41.73 min (3-linked hexose). The loss of fragment m/z 60 is due to the formation of the stable product acetic acid and the loss of m/z 42 is due to the formation of ketene. The loss of fragment m/z 32 is due to the formation of the stable product methanol and the loss of m/z 30 is due to the formation of formaldehyde.

Peak (m/z)	Primary Fragment	Fragmentation Loss
86	118 234	-32 -2(32), -2(42)
87	161	-32, -42
99	161 233	-32, -30 -60, -32, -42
101	161 277	-60 -60, -32, -2(42)
118	C1 – C2	Fragment between C2-C3
129	161 277	-32 -2(32), -2(42)
143	233 277	-60, -30 -60, -32, -42
160	234	-32, -42
161	C4 – C6	Fragment between C3-C4
175	277	-60, -42
202	234	-32
203	277	-32, -42
217	277	-60
234	C1 – C4	Fragment between C4-C5
245	277	-32

The 4-linked *N*-acetylgalactosamine, which has the retention time of 72.46 minutes, has no vicinal diol and, appropriately, remained intact. The fragmentation pattern (Figure 44) was identical to the one in the non-oxidized sample (Figure 32) and had both the characteristic peaks: for the linkage with m/z 173, 233 and a minor peak at 203; and the presence of the methylated acetamido group m/z 75, 99, 117 and 159.

The results from the Smith degradation method can provide hints for determining the backbone of the CPS structure. It was observed that the two sugars linked at the 2,3 site of the 2,3-linked galactose were susceptible to the degradation process, indicating there was a presence of vicinal diols; the presence of 2-linked galactose was much higher than the presence of the 3-linked galactose from the degraded 2,3-galactose residue which indicates that the 2-linked site is part of the backbone. The 2,3-linked mannose only had one susceptible sugar at the 2-linked site which indicates that the 3-linked site of the mannose is part of the backbone structure. The sites of these 2,3-linked hexoses which were much lower in intensity likely have terminal glucoses present.

The 4-linked glucose appeared to remain constant from the non-oxidized sample to the oxidized sample, which should have been degraded, indicating that the PMAA derived sample was likely contaminated; this is supported with the AA derived Smith degraded sample showing that nearly all the glucose residue was destroyed (Table 12).

Figure 35. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the terminal glucose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 36.47 min in the GC-MS. The primary fragmented molecules were formed through the loss of the stable products acetic acid (m/z 60) and methanol (m/z 32); the secondary fragment losses are from formaldehyde (m/z 30) and ketene (m/z 42).

Figure 36. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the terminal galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,5-di-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 37.68 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 37. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 4-linked glucose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,4,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 41.36 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 38. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 2-linked galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-3,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 41.92 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 39. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 3-linked galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,3,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 42.26 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 40. PMAA EI mass spectrum of the Smith degradation 2,3-linked galactose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,3,5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-4,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 2,3-linked hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 46.27 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 41. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 2-linked mannose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-3,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 40.24 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 42. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 3-linked mannose. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,3,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-2,4,6-tri-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a terminal hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 41.73 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 43. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 2,3-linked mannose. An electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,2,3,5-tetra-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-4,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 2,3-linked hexose after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 45.49 min in the GC-MS.

Figure 44. Smith degraded PMAA EI mass spectrum of the 4-linked *N*-acetylgalactosamine. Shown is the electron impact (EI) fragmentation pattern of a 1,4,5-tri-*O*-acetyl-(1-deuterio)-(2-*N*-methylacetamide)-3,6-di-*O*-methyl hexitol, a partially methylated alditol acetate derivative of a 4-linked *N*-acetylhexosamine after periodate oxidation, at the retention time of 72.46 min in the GC-MS.

4.4. Structural analysis by NMR

4.4.1. One-dimensional NMR ^1H (Proton) NMR

The initial information gathered from the ^1H spectrum at 295 K indicated the presence of five anomeric protons in the $\delta_{\text{H}} \sim 4.4 - 5.5$ ppm range^[74]; however, based on the 1D ^1H NMR at 326 K and 2D ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC NMR results, it was determined there were eight anomeric peaks with three in the α -anomeric configuration and the other five in the β -anomeric configuration. The proton at $\delta_{\text{H}} \sim 2.0$ ppm is the presence of the methyl group of the acetamido (*N*-acetyl, NAc) group of the GalNAc residue. By raising the temperature, the anomeric proton peaks becomes isolated and the peak splitting between almost all eight anomeric peaks becomes distinct as the ^3J -coupling becomes greater than 3 Hz; the exception to this is peak H_D1 which remains as an unresolved doublet at 326 K, implying that the spin system D is the 2,3-linked mannose, determined by the sugar linkage analysis, as it is the only possible carbohydrate identified that could have a $^3\text{J} < 3$ Hz due to the H_D2 being in the equatorial position.

Figure 45. One-dimensional ^1H NMR result at (A, black) 295 K and (B, red) 326 K of a dialyzed (1000 MWCO) 4.0% acetic acid-treated CPS.

4.4.2. ^1H - ^1H Correlation Spectroscopy (COSY)

The anomeric protons are easy to identify as their chemical shifts are downfield from the other ring protons due to the deshielding from the two attached oxygens in the acetal functional group. To assign the other protons present, the two-dimensional (2D) homonuclear technique (^1H - ^1H) COSY is done as the cross peaks are formed between two protons which are connected within a few bonds, including vicinal protons.

At 295 K (Figure 46), only the second proton of each spin system could be identified by the cross peak with the anomeric proton; there was too much overlaps at the ring proton region which made it extremely difficult to resolve any protons past ^1H -2.

In order to see the cross peaks of all the anomers, a COSY was ran at 326 K which shifted to the HOD peak upfield (to the right) to a region with no peaks being overlapped, unlike the spectrum at 295 K which overlaps peaks D and E. In addition, at 326 K, it is now possible to obtain the cross peaks for F, G and H as these peaks are now located to the right of the ring proton region and are connectable. The assigned cross peaks can be found on Table 19 on page 97.

Figure 46. A ^1H - ^1H COSY of *Clostridium perfringens* at 295 K. Assignments of the proton past ^1H -2 cannot be done due to a lot of overlapping cross peaks in the ring proton region.

Figure 47. A ^1H - ^1H COSY of the anomeric proton region at 326 K.

4.4.3. ^1H - ^{13}C Heteronuclear Single Quantum Correlation spectroscopy (^1H - ^{13}C HSQC)

A ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC is done to identify and assign the ^{13}C chemical shift to the attached proton by observing the cross peaks to which the protons were identified by various techniques mentioned previously - including 2D ^1H - ^1H COSY and 1D-TOCSY. The chemical shift for each system seen from HSQC (and HMBC) is listed on Table 17 on page 83.

Figure 48. ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC result at 295 K of a 4.0% acetic acid treated CPS.

4.4.4. ^1H - ^{13}C Heteronuclear Multiple Bonds Correlation spectroscopy (^1H - ^{13}C HMBC)

A ^1H – ^{13}C HMBC is used to figure out what two nuclei are connected within 3 bonds by assigning the observed $^1\text{H}(x)$ and $^{13}\text{C}(y)$ signals to the signals obtained from previous NMR techniques such as the ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC. Only peaks A and D were unable to be seen in the HMBC. A method of identifying the connection of the peak was to overlay the HMBC result with the HSQC result so the carbon/proton origin can be discovered.

The anomeric peaks B and C had their protons chemical shift present in the anomeric region and the carbon chemical shift was the same as the third carbon of the ring. The remainder of the peaks had the anomeric carbon chemical shift with the proton referring to another atom. Unfortunately, due to the overlaps of the ring regions, the assignment of peaks E, F, G could not be properly made out as the δ_{H} were in a region with proton overlaps. For system H, the only assignable cross peak for the HMBC, appeared to have the carbon shift for $\text{C}_{\text{H}1}$ at the same location as the proton chemical shift matching that of $\delta_{\text{H}}(\text{D}3)$ which was determined by 1D-TOCSY & 1D-NOESY techniques.

Figure 49. ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC result at 295 K. The black data set is the magnitude HMBC result; the red (positive contour) and pink (negative contour) is the ^1H – ^{13}C HSQC data.

Table 17. ^1H and ^{13}C chemical shifts (in ppm) obtained by ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC and HMBC. The values were obtained at 295 K

Spin system	δH1	δH2
	δC1	δC2
A	5.50 101.8	3.93 61.2
B	5.18 103.5	4.14 79.7
C	5.17 95.79	3.69 70.9
D	4.84 103.1	4.41 76.9
E	4.79 106.1	3.34 73.6
F	4.74 106.1	3.40 69.6
G	4.62 106.1	3.37 73.23
H	4.51 103.95	3.94 70.84

4.4.5. ^1H 1D-Selective Total Correlation Spectroscopy (1D-TOCSY)

A selective ^1H 1D-TOCSY was performed by magnetizing an isolated peak, in this case the anomeric protons, which magnetizes the protons present in the same spin system; for carbohydrates, this means that we can see the protons present on the selected carbohydrate.

The advantage of selective 1D-TOCSY over its 2D variant is the lower time needed (minutes/hours vs days) and the ability to irradiate a peak of interest to see the protons in the same spin system. Using both a 1D-TOCSY and a ^1H - ^1H COSY, at the same temperature, helps aid in identifying the proton position seen in the ring.

The spin systems F, G and H were able to have all their protons assigned by the use of COSY at 326 K as well as their peak splitting. System A and H could only be assigned up to proton 4 and the peaks of system D could not be identified by 1D-TOCSY at 326 K. Based on the splitting patterns observed, system E-G were all determined to be glucose and system H appears to have a splitting pattern similar to galactose.

Figure 50. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak A1 at 326 K.

Figure 51. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak B1 at 326 K.

Figure 52. 1D TOCSY with water suppression result from irradiating the peak B3 at 326 K

Figure 53. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak C1 at 326 K.

Figure 54. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak E1 at 326 K.

Figure 55. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak F1 at 326 K.

Figure 56. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak G1 at 326 K. Assignment of G2, G4 and G5 locations were possible from assigning the peaks with the 326 K COSY.

Figure 57. 1D TOCSY result from irradiating the anomeric peak H1 at 326 K.

4.4.6. ^1H 1D-Selective Nuclear Overhauser Effect Spectroscopy (1D-NOESY)

A selective ^1H 1D-NOESY was performed by irradiating an isolated peak, primarily the anomeric protons, which allows the excitation of atoms within 5 Å through space.^[72] As mentioned in the last section, the advantage of selective 1D-NOESY over its 2D variant is the lower time needed (minutes/hours vs days) and the ability to irradiate a peak of interest to see the protons in the same spin system. Using 1D-TOCSY helps identify the proton within the same spin ring which, when the TOCSY peaks are eliminated from the 1D-NOESY results, can deduce what peaks are nearby the irradiated peak which are not part of the same spin system.

Various nearby protons were shown but it was confirmed, with two NOESY results being conclusive, that: anomeric peak B1 is nearby H4; anomeric peak C1 sees peak A4; anomeric peak E1 sees B3; anomeric peak F1 sees B2; and anomeric peak G1 sees D2.

Figure 58. 1D NOESY result at 326 K from irradiating the anomeric peak A1 overlaid with TOCSY results for all spin system except system C. The peak labelled with '*m*' means there's multiple/overlapping peaks for the possibility; here being from A2, C3, D3, E6', or H2.

Figure 59. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak A4 at 326 K.

Figure 60. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak B1 at 326 K. The *m* signifies that there's a multiple choice that this peak could be from spins E6 or H3.

Figure 61. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak B2 at 326 K.

Figure 62. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak B3 at 326 K.

Figure 63. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak C1 at 326 K.

Figure 64. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak D1 at 326 K. The peak labelled *m1* signifies that there's a multiple choice that this peak could be D3 (very likely), A2, C3 or H2. The label *m2* means a possibility that the peak is either C2 or F4.

Figure 65. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak D2 at 326 K. The peak labelled *m* could be the D3 (likely), A2, C3 or G2 peak.

Figure 66. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak E1 at 326 K.

Figure 67. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak F1 at 326 K. The peak labelled *m1* signifies that there's a multiple choice that this peak could be a peak E6, F3 or H3. The label *m2* means a possibility that the peak is either F5 or G6'.

Figure 68. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak G1 at 326 K.

Figure 69. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak H1 at 326 K. The peak labelled *m* is very likely D3 but can potentially be peak E6.

Figure 70. 1D NOESY result from irradiating peak H4 at 326 K. The peak C6 could potentially be accidentally selected/present from a wide selection when irradiation of H4.

4.4.7. 2D NMR on the Smith-degraded capsular polysaccharide

The ^1H - ^1H COSY, at 295 K, shows that spin system A remained intact; this narrows the possibility of system A likely being the 4-linked GalNAc which would make system H, the only other spin system with a 4-linked site determined by NMR, a 4-linked glucose.

Figure 71. A ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC at 295 K on the Smith-degraded CPS. The peaks and labels in red is the COSY from the intact CPS whereas peaks and labels in black is the Smith-degraded CPS.

Figure 72. A ^1H - ^1H COSY at 295 K on the Smith-degraded CPS. The peaks in red is the COSY from the intact CPS and the ^1H spectrum in green belongs to the intact CPS; peaks in black is the Smith-degraded CPS.

Table 18. ^1H and ^{13}C chemical shifts (in ppm) of a Smith degraded *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 capsular polysaccharide measured by ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC at 295 K.

Smith Peak	δH1 (ppm)	δC1 (ppm)	From intact CPS Peak
I	5.50	104.0	A
II	5.26	103.8	Likely from B
III	5.28	94.0	Likely from C
IV	4.98	103.3	Likely from D
V	4.78	102.7	Likely from D
VI	4.72	103.7	Likely from B
VII	4.69	106.5	
VIII	4.64	107.1	

4.5. Summary of the structure thus far

The capsular polysaccharide for *Clostridium perfringens* has currently been solved to three fragments thus far (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The link between systems H1 and D3 was observed with HMBC on the intact CPS structure (Figure 49). The link sites of A1, D2 and H1 have yet to be conclusively identified which would determine how all the fragments are link together.

Based on the splitting pattern of the protons seen in the 1D TOCSY for systems E (Figure 54) and F (Figure 55), it can be assumed to be a glucose unit due to the large splitting observed for ¹H-3 and ¹H-4 due to the higher ³J-coupling (> 4 Hz) as all the protons, except for the anomeric proton, would be approximately 180° apart. Based on the Hg3 splitting pattern, it also appears to be a glucose unit. By the HSQC of the Smith degraded sample (Figure 71), System A is likely the 4-linked GalNAc residue and system H is a 4-linked glucose. It has been determined by the Smith degradation method that the link sites of B2 and C3 are part of the backbone structure. By the process of elimination, this means that the last unknown residue, system C, is likely a 3-linked galactose peak – which is also indicated by the short-long splitting for Hc4.

The *Clostridium perfringens* capsular polysaccharide has yet to be fully characterized but has been found thus far to be an oligosaccharide repeat unit containing →4)-β-D-Glc-(1→3)-D-Gal(1→, →2)-[β-D-Glc-(1→3)]-α-D-Gal-(1→, →4)-α-D-GalNAc-(1→ and →3)-[β-D-Glc-(1→2)]-β-D-Man-(1→ (Figure 73).

Figure 73. The fragments of the *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 capsular polysaccharide identified thus far.

Table 19. ^1H and ^{13}C chemical shifts (in ppm) and the coupling constant of the anomeric protons (in Hz) of *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 capsular polysaccharide. δ_{H} and ^3J values were measured at 326 K and δ_{C} were obtained at 295 K by various NMR techniques. The first column will contain the name of the monosaccharide if identified through the methods above with the spin system in superscript or have the spin system in its place if the monosaccharide has yet to be determined; note that the numbers, or T – which stands for terminal, in front are the linkage site for that residue.

Link-Residue [spin system]	$^3\text{J}_{\text{H1,H}2}$ at 326 K	δH1^{326} δH1^{295} δC1^{295}	δH2^{326} δH2^{295} δC2^{295}	δH3^{326} δH3^{295} δC3^{295}	δH4^{326} δH4^{295} δC4^{295}	δH5^{326} δH5^{295} δC5^{295}	δH6^{326} δH6^{295} δC6^{295}	$\delta\text{H6}'^{326}$ $\delta\text{H6}'^{295}$ $\delta\text{C6}'^{295}$
4- α -GalNAc [A]	3.96	5.46 5.50 101.8	3.93 3.93 61.2	4.05 4.06 78.2	4.26 4.25 67.8			
2,3- α -Gal [B]	3.48	5.19 5.18 103.5	4.14 4.14 79.7	4.30 4.30 68.8				
[C]	3.60	5.15 5.17 95.79	3.69 3.69 70.9	3.84 3.83 83.1	3.94 3.95 70.9			
2,3- β -Man [D]	< 3	4.84 4.84 103.1	4.42 4.41 76.9	3.96 3.95 74.1				
T- β -Glc [E]	7.86	4.78 4.79 106.1	3.34 3.34 73.6	3.51 3.52 76.0	3.43 3.43 76.1	3.49 3.49 76.0	3.76 3.75 59.9	3.91 3.92 59.9
[F]	7.80	4.72 4.74 106.1	3.39 3.40 69.6	3.72 3.73 72.2	3.66 3.67 78.5	3.62 3.63 74.7	3.89 3.91 59.9	3.74 3.75 59.9
T- β -Glc [G]	7.68	4.65 4.62 106.1	3.38 3.37 73.23	3.44 3.43 69.6	3.35 3.34 73.6	3.37 3.38 76.7	3.90 3.91 59.8	3.64 3.64 59.8
[H]	8.28	4.55 4.51 103.95	3.93 3.94 70.84	3.75 3.74 75.60	4.07 4.06 78.33			

4.6. Future work on this project

Final structural confirmation has to be done by repeating a more intense ^1H - ^{13}C HMBC to confirm the linkages of the units in addition to completing the chemical shifts of the missing ring protons. Oxidation and conjugation of the CPS to an antigenic carrier to produce a glycoconjugate vaccine remains to be done.

CHAPTER 5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE *CLOSTRIDIUM BOLTEAE* STRAINS 16351 AND 14578 CAPSULAR POLYSACCHARIDE

5.1. Potential energy surface

The potential energy surface (PES) scan was performed at the HF/6-31G*, for both the optimization and energy calculations, with the molecules in gas phase without any implicit solvent defined. The modelled fragments of *C. bolteae* CPS shows that the glycosidic torsion angles of the 3-OMe- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-Rhap-OMe (aDm-bDr) residue (Figure 74A) has the phi angle limited to an approximate range of -60° to $+60^\circ$ [$\phi \in (-60^\circ, +60^\circ)$]; within this phi range, the psi angle has more flexibility with no energy limitation but strongly prefers to be within the range -60° to $+60^\circ$ as well [$\psi \in (-60^\circ, +60^\circ)$]. In addition, there is another, small, preferred range which exists at $\phi \in (-60^\circ, \pm 0^\circ)$, $\psi \in (+150^\circ, -120^\circ)$.

The range of the glycosidic angles is almost the opposite for the 4-OMe- β -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe (bDr-aDm) residue (Figure 74B) where the phi angle is not limited when the psi angle is between -45° and $+60^\circ$ though it would prefer to be within the range of $+60^\circ$ to -150° ; in addition, there is another larger range that the glycosidic angle for this residue would prefer, that being $\phi \in (-30^\circ, +90^\circ)$ when $\psi \in (-60^\circ, -180^\circ)$.

The enantiomer of the rhamnose unit was modelled to observe the difference in the PES from the *C. bolteae* CPS, where the rhamnose is in the D-configuration, in the more preferable L-configuration. The most obvious difference is the increase in the difference of energy for the aDm-bLr (3-OMe- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -L-Rhap-OMe) residue (Figure 74C) compared to the aDm-bDr (Figure 74A) and this is reflected in the overall ΔE as seen in

Table 20. The most preferable torsion angle zone appears to be $\phi \in (-60^\circ, -30^\circ)$ when $\psi \in (-30^\circ, 0^\circ)$. For the bLr-aDm (4-OMe- β -L-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe) residue (Figure 74D), it reflects a similar energy level as the bDr-aDm residue with a preferable torsion region of $\phi \in (-30^\circ, +90^\circ)$ when $\psi \in (-60^\circ, -180^\circ)$ and $\phi \in (+30^\circ, -150^\circ)$ when $\psi \in (-30^\circ, +90^\circ)$.

The opposite anomer of the *C. bolteae* CPS was modelled to observe the change in the preference of the torsion angles CPS if the opposite anomeric configuration was present. The first observable impact is that the figures of the Man-Rha and Rha-Man disaccharides torsion angles for Figure 75 appears as the mirror opposite of Figure 74. Unlike the large preferences observed for the 4-OMe- β -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe unit (Figure 74B), the torsion angle for 3-OMe- β -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap-OMe (Figure 75A) prefers the smaller torsion range of $\phi \in (+120^\circ, -165^\circ)$ and $\psi \in (-45^\circ, +30^\circ)$. The 4-OMe- α -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -D-Manp-OMe unit (Figure 75B) has only one preferable region at $\phi \in (-60^\circ, +30^\circ)$ and $\psi \in (-90^\circ, +90^\circ)$. It should be noted that the maximum energy value for the bDm-aDr value is higher than the other modelled disaccharide units (Table 20).

Finally, the last modelled structure shown is the naturally abundant configuration for the carbohydrates of the CPS; this means that the rhamnose unit here is α -L-rhamnose in place of the β -D-rhamnose of the actual CPS unit. The first modelled disaccharide unit 3-OMe- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-Rhap-OMe (aDm-aLr) residue (Figure 77A) appears to be similar to that of the aDm-bDr modelled CPS unit; it has a torsion preference of $\phi \in (-60^\circ, -15^\circ)$ and $\psi \in (-60^\circ, +30^\circ)$. The second modelled unit, 4-OMe- α -L-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe (aLr-aDm) unit (Figure 77B), is different than the other modelled CPS units. The

preference torsion zone is more circular with the preferred torsion angle being $\phi \in (-60^\circ, -30^\circ)$ and $\psi \in (-60^\circ, +60^\circ)$.

Table 20. The minimum and maximum energy (in kcal/mol) for each modelled disaccharide with the phi and psi torsion angle. Energy level obtained from a potential energy surface scan at HF/6-31G*. The overall ΔE is calculated by subtracting the energy value with the highest energy value.

Model	Energy level (min/max)	Energy (kcal/mol)	Overall ΔE (kcal/mol)	Phi (ϕ , in $^\circ$)	Psi (ψ , in $^\circ$)
aDm-bDr	Min	-811 884.53	-42.27	-30	-30
	Max	-811 849.85	-7.59	150	120
bDr-aDm	Min	-811 881.92	-39.66	30	-174
	Max	-811 855.06	-12.80	-90	120
aDm-bLr	Min	-811 886.20	-43.94	-30	-30
	Max	-811 842.26	0.00	150	120
bLr-aDm	Min	-811 876.81	-34.55	180	0
	Max	-811 849.83	-7.57	-90	120
bDm-aDr	Min	-811 887.55	-45.29	173	-7
	Max	-811 858.77	-16.51	-127	113
aDr-bDm	Min	-811 881.52	-39.26	-47	-24
	Max	-811 849.46	-7.20	133	126
aDm-aLr	Min	-811 890.43	-48.17	-30	-30
	Max	-811 845.18	-2.92	150	120
aLr-aDm	Min	-811 881.41	-39.15	-30	60
	Max	-811 848.88	-6.62	120	120

Figure 74. The PES for the anomer of the *C. bolteae* CPS. A differential energy plot (ΔE , in kcal/mol) based on the torsion angles ϕ and ψ for the disaccharides: (A) aDm-bDr, methyl 4-*O*-(3-*O*-methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- β -D-rhamnopyranoside; (B) bDr-aDm, methyl 3-*O*-(4-*O*-methyl- β -D-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside; (C) aDm-bLr, methyl 4-*O*-(3-*O*-methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- β -L-rhamnopyranoside; and (D) bLr-aDm, methyl 3-*O*-(4-*O*-methyl- β -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside.

Figure 75. Contour map of the PES of the disaccharide models of the *C. bolteae* CPS. A differential energy plot (ΔE , in kcal/mol) based on the torsion angles ϕ and ψ for the disaccharides: (A) bDm-aDr, methyl 4-*O*-(3-*O*-methyl- β -D-mannopyranosyl)- α -D-rhamnopyranoside; and (B) aDr-bDm, methyl 3-*O*-(4-*O*-methyl- α -D-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-mannopyranoside.

Figure 76. Contour map of the PES of the naturally abundant configuration of the mannose-rhamnose disaccharide model. A differential energy plot (ΔE , in kcal/mol) based on the torsion angles ϕ and ψ for the disaccharides: (A) aDm-aLr, methyl 4-*O*-(3-*O*-methyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside; and (B) aLr-aDm, methyl 3-*O*-(4-*O*-methyl- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- α -D-mannopyranoside.

5.2. Molecular dynamic simulation

5.2.1. Trisaccharide unit in an implicit solvent

Knowing the regions where the torsions are likely to occur from the PES is helpful in determining the conformation the polysaccharide can take but there is still a large region of possibilities for the torsion and not to discount the fact that the simulation was done in gas phase. The next question is what is the impact of adding the solvent to the system and how does this impact the preferred torsion regions. To answer this, a non-methylated trisaccharide unit [α -D-Man p (1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Man p] was subjected to a 50 ns implicit molecular dynamic simulation with the dielectric constant set to 78.5 to mimic a system where the solvent is water.

The preferred torsion angles observed along the mannose glycosidic bond, within 97.5% of the range, were $(\phi_M, \psi_M)_{97.5\%} = (-37^\circ \pm 37^\circ, -26^\circ \pm 26^\circ)$. It could be seen in Figure 78 that there were two sets of data point present where both sets of points fell in the low energy region determined in the PES; the majority at $(\phi_{M1}, \psi_{M1})_{99.95\%} = (-37^\circ \pm 45^\circ, -26^\circ \pm 59^\circ)$ and the minority at $(\phi_{M2}, \psi_{M2})_{99.95\%} = (+31^\circ \pm 45^\circ, +11^\circ \pm 34^\circ)$. The torsion angle observed along the rhamnose glycosidic bond was not as restrained in the low energy area as that was observed for the mannose glycosidic torsion. Within 97.5% of the range, the torsion angles were $(\phi_R, \psi_R)_{97.5\%} = (+49^\circ \pm 44^\circ, +24^\circ \pm 58^\circ)$ and two data sets were seen: the majority at $(\phi_{R1}, \psi_{R1})_{99.95\%} = (+49^\circ \pm 51^\circ, +24^\circ \pm 81^\circ)$ and the minority at $(\phi_{R2}, \psi_{R2})_{99.80\%} = (-44^\circ \pm 51^\circ, -11^\circ \pm 67^\circ)$.

Figure 77. The torsion angles of the trisaccharide unit in implicit solution over time. The glycosidic torsion angles, ϕ and ψ , respectively, of the (A,B) mannose and (C,D) rhamnose units of the trisaccharide unit, α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp, for a 50 ns molecular dynamic simulation in an implicit water solvent.

Figure 78. The frequency of the torsion angles of the trisaccharide unit in implicit solution over time. The glycosidic torsion angles, ϕ and ψ , respectively, of the (A-C) mannose and (D-F) rhamnose units of the trisaccharide unit, α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp, for a 50 ns molecular dynamic simulation in an implicit water solvent. Figures (C,F) have the torsion angles of mannose and rhamnose, respectively, plotted on to the filled contour map of the PES of the methylated disaccharides (respectively 3-OMe- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-Rhap-OMe and 4-OMe- β -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp-OMe) from Figure 74; the saturation of the blue was lowered for clarity and the ΔE is in kcal/mol, relative to the energy of the bDm-aDr unit.

5.2.2. Decarepeat oligosaccharide in an explicit solvent

The difference between the implicit and explicit solvation model is how the energy is treated to the molecule; the implicit solvation affects the whole molecule evenly whereas the explicit model affects only the parts that the molecule collides with. There were two decarepeat models that were subjected to an explicit water (TIP3P) molecular dynamics: the *C. bolteae* CPS, [\rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-Rhap(1 \rightarrow)]₁₀, and its most abundant configuration [\rightarrow 3)- α -D-Manp(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-Rhap(1 \rightarrow)]₁₀.

5.2.2.1. The *Clostridium bolteae* CPS (aDm-bDr)

The overall confirmation of the polysaccharide is a hallow helix with a seven repeating units (i+6) per turn. The angle of rotation is approximately 51.4° with an average pitch of approximately 18.4 Å. Most of the residue are in the ⁴C₁ ($\theta = 0^\circ$) configuration with the exception of mannose residue 8 (M8) where it went in to the ²S₀ ($\varphi = 150^\circ, \theta = 90^\circ$), ^B_{3,0} ($\varphi = 180^\circ, \theta = 90^\circ$) and ¹S₃ ($\varphi = 210^\circ, \theta = 90^\circ$) configurations after 2.75 ns in the simulation where the polysaccharide was twisting; the rhamnose units did not show any differentiation from their ⁴C₁ configuration over the simulation time. For the mannose residue, the ratio of the χ^5 exocyclic torsion angle being in the *gt:gg:tg* conformation was approximately 87.82 : 12.11 : 0.06.

Figure 79. The helical conformation of the aDm-bDr polysaccharide. The polysaccharide at 5 ns of explicit TIP3P water molecular dynamic simulation. All the even, green residues are the mannose and all odd, teal residues are rhamnose units.

Figure 80. The glycosidic torsion angles present in the explicit TIP3P water molecular dynamic simulation plotted on the PES of the aDm-bDr and bDr-aDm modelled disaccharide units.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 81. The result of a molecular dynamic simulation for the mannose residues (A) 8, (B) 10 and (C) 12 of the *C. bolteae* CPS model. The series of plots shows, over time (in ns), the residue's torsion angles (in $^\circ$): (I) phi, ϕ ; (II) psi, ψ ; (III) chi-5, χ^5 ; and the puckering parameters (IV) pseudorotational phase angle (φ , in $^\circ$); (V) magnitude of the distortion of the ring (θ , in $^\circ$); and (VI) total puckering amplitude (Q , in \AA).

Figure 82. A histogram of the χ^5 *tg:gg:gt* conformation in the explicit molecular dynamic simulation for the mannose residues (A) 8, (B) 10 and (C) 12 for the *C. bolteae* CPS model.

Figure 83. A Hammer-Aitoff projection of the puckering coordinates (ϕ , θ) of the explicit molecular dynamic simulation model for the mannose residues (A) 8 (M8) and (B) 10 (M10); and (C) rhamnose residue 11 (R11) for the *C. bolteae* CPS model.

Figure 84. The result of a molecular dynamic simulation for the rhamnose residues (A) 11 and (B) 13 for the *C. bolteae* CPS model. The series of plots shows, over time (in ns), the residue's torsion angles (in $^{\circ}$): (I) phi, ϕ and (II) psi, ψ ; and the puckering parameters (III) pseudorotational phase angle (φ , in $^{\circ}$); (IV) magnitude of the distortion of the ring (θ , in $^{\circ}$); and (V) total puckering amplitude (Q , in \AA).

5.2.2.2. The most abundant configuration (aDm-aLr)

The overall confirmation of the polysaccharide is a helix with a four repeating units (i+3) per turn. The angle of rotation of the helix is 90° and the average pitch is approximately 9.83 \AA . All of the α -L-rhamnose residues were in the 1C_4 ($\theta = 180^\circ$) configuration and most of the mannose residues were in the 4C_1 ($\theta = 0^\circ$) configuration with the exception of mannose residues 2, 10 and 14 where it went in to the $B_{3,0}$ ($\varphi = 180^\circ, \theta = 90^\circ$) configurations either briefly or, for M2, for approximately 1 ns (Figure 87 and Figure 90). For the mannose residue, the ratio of the χ^5 exocyclic torsion angle being in the *gt:gg:tg* conformation was approximately 80.18 : 19.71 : 0.11 (Figure 88).

Figure 85. The helical conformation of the aDm-aLr polysaccharide. The polysaccharide at 5 ns of explicit TIP3P water molecular dynamic simulation. All the even residues (green outline) are the mannose residue and the rhamnose residues are coloured teal.

Figure 86. The glycosidic torsion angles present in the explicit TIP3P water molecular dynamic simulation plotted on the PES of the aDm-aLr and aLr-aDm modelled disaccharide units.

Figure 87. The result of a molecular dynamic simulation for the mannose residues (A) 10 and (B) 12 for the most abundant (aDm-aLr) model. The series of plots shows, over time (in ns), the residue's torsion angles (in $^{\circ}$): (I) phi, ϕ ; (II) psi, ψ ; (III) chi-5, χ^5 ; and the puckering parameters (IV) pseudorotational phase angle (ϕ , in $^{\circ}$); (V) magnitude of the distortion of the ring (θ , in $^{\circ}$); and (VI) total puckering amplitude (Q , in \AA).

Figure 88. A histogram of the χ^5 *tg:gg:gt* conformation in the explicit molecular dynamic simulation for the mannose residues (A) 10 and (B) 12 for the most abundant (aDm-aLr) model.

Figure 89. A Hammer-Aitoff projection of the puckering coordinates (φ, θ) of the explicit molecular dynamic simulation model for the (A) mannose residue 10 (M10) and (B) rhamnose residue 11 (R11) for the most abundant (aDm-aLr) model. Note that the M10 residue was in the boat/skewed form for ~ 0.05 ns as can be seen in Figure 87A-V.

Figure 90. The result of a molecular dynamic simulation for the rhamnose residues (A) 11 and (B) 13 for the most abundant (aDm-aLr) model. The series of plots shows, over time (in ns), the residue's torsion angles (in °): (I) phi, ϕ and (II) psi, ψ ; and the puckering parameters (III) pseudorotational phase angle (ϕ , in °); (IV) magnitude of the distortion of the ring (θ , in °); and (V) total puckering amplitude (Q , in Å).

5.2.3. Summary of the polysaccharide conformation analysis of *Clostridium bolteae*

The *Clostridium bolteae* capsular polysaccharide has been determined by explicit water molecular dynamics to be in a right-handed hollow helix conformation with a seven turn repeat. The torsional angle for both the mannose and rhamnose units reflected the methylated disaccharide unit modelled for the potential energy surface. The exocyclic torsion angle χ^5 (O5/C4-C5-C6-O6) for the C5-C6 conformation for the mannose residue highly preferred the *gt* conformation at approximately 87.8% followed by the *gg* conformation at ~12.1% and the *tg* conformation was highly unfavourable with < 0.1% presence during the simulation.

The derivative of the *C. bolteae* CPS where the β -D-rhamnose was replaced with the most abundant form, α -L-rhamnose, was done at the same time for observation of the difference in the overall conformation. The largest impact was that the overall polysaccharide conformation was more of a rigid right-handed helix with a four turn repeat. It was also observed that the rhamnose unit's torsional angle from the molecular dynamic simulation did not fall within the most favourable angles as determined by the potential energy surface; this is likely due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the tighter helix.

The conformation of each residue depends where the residue is during the simulation; mannose units in midst of the twist of the helix tended to be in the $B_{3,0}$ or 1S_3 configuration whereas the rhamnose units tended to remain in their initial configuration.

5.2.4. Future work on this project

A NOE-restrained molecular dynamic simulation is planned as well as a comparison of the theoretical models value to the experimentally obtained values such as determining the conformation of the compound by observing the coupling constant.

CHAPTER 6. CONCLUSIONS

6.1. *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 capsular polysaccharide structural analysis

The capsular polysaccharide, based on the results obtained by GC-MS and NMR, is found to contain the following components: $\rightarrow 4$)- β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 3)-D-Gal(1 \rightarrow , \rightarrow 2)-[β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- α -D-Gal-(1 \rightarrow , \rightarrow 4)- α -D-GalNAc-(1 \rightarrow and \rightarrow 3)-[β -D-Glc-(1 \rightarrow 2)]- β -D-Man-(1 \rightarrow (Figure 73).

Figure 73. The fragments of the *Clostridium perfringens* strain 1395 capsular polysaccharide identified thus far.

6.2. *Clostridium bolteae* polysaccharide conformational analysis

The capsular polysaccharide of *Clostridium bolteae* strains 16351 and 14578 was determined, by running a 5 ns explicit water-solvation molecular dynamics simulation in AMBER, to exist as a right-handed hollow helix with a seven residues present per turn. The population analysis of the exocyclic conformation of the mannose residue showed that the majority of the exocyclic torsion angle between C5 and C6 ($\chi_5 = \text{O5/C4} - \text{C5} - \text{C6} - \text{O6}$) preferred *gauche-trans* (*gt*) configuration at ~88% followed by ~12% of the structure's preference being in the *gauche-gauche* (*gg*) configuration; there was no preference for the *trans-gauche* (*tg*) conformation as it was < 1%.

Figure 79. The helical conformation of the aDm-bDr polysaccharide. The polysaccharide at 5 ns of explicit TIP3P water molecular dynamic simulation. All the even, green residues are the mannose and all odd, teal residues are rhamnose units.

CHAPTER 7. REFERENCES

1. Biermann, C. J.; McGinnis, G. D. Analysis of Carbohydrates by GLC and MS; CRC Press, Inc.: Boca Raton, Florida, 1989.
2. Rini, J. M.; Leffler, H. Carbohydrate Recognition and Signaling. In *Handbook of Cell Signaling*, 1 ed; Bradshaw, R. A., Dennis, E. A. (Eds.); Academic Press: San Diego, California, 2003, Vol. 1, pp 87-93.
3. Pigman, W. W.; Goepf, R. M. Chemistry of the Carbohydrates; Academic Press: New York, 1948.
4. Solomons, T. W. G.; Fryhle, C. B. Organic Chemistry, 10th ed.; John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: Hoboken, New Jersey, 2011.
5. Hart, H.; Craine, L. E.; Hadad, C. M. Organic chemistry: a short course, 11th ed.; Houghton Mifflin Company: 2011.
6. McNaught, A. *Adv. Carbohydr. Chem. Biochem.*, **1997**, 52, 43-117.
7. Sinnott, M. Carbohydrate Chemistry and Biochemistry: Structure and Mechanism; RSC Publishing: 2007.
8. Lindhorst, T. K. Essentials of Carbohydrate Chemistry and Biochemistry, 2nd edition ed.; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany, 2003.
9. IUPAC. *Pure Appl. Chem.*, **1981**, 53, 1901-1905.
10. Stick, R. V.; Williams, S. Carbohydrates: The Essential Molecules of Life; Elsevier Science: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2010.
11. Barnett, C. B.; Naidoo, K. J. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, **2010**, 114, 17142-17154.
12. Pequegnat, B.; Sagermann, M.; Valliani, M.; Toh, M.; Chow, H.; Allen-Vercoe, E.; Monteiro, M. A. *Vaccine*, **2013**, 31, 2787-2790.
13. Karplus, M. *The Journal of chemical physics*, **1959**, 30, 11-15.
14. Clayden, J.; Greeves, N.; Warren, S. Organic Chemistry, 2nd ed.; OUP Oxford: 2012.
15. Wang, Q.; Cui, S. W. Understanding the conformation of polysaccharides. In *Food Carbohydrates: Chemistry, Physical Properties, and Applications*, ed; Cui, S. W. (Ed.), CRC Press: Boca Raton, Florida, 2005, Vol. 219,
16. Belitz, H. D.; Grosch, W.; Schieberle, P. Food Chemistry; Springer: 2009.

17. Leboffe, M. J.; Pierce, B. E. *Microbiology: Laboratory Theory and Application*; Morton Publishing Company: 2012.
18. Engelkirk, P. G.; Duben-Engelkirk, J. L. *Laboratory Diagnosis of Infectious Diseases: Essentials of Diagnostic Microbiology*; Wolters Kluwer Health/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins: 2008.
19. Esko, J. D.; Doering, T. L.; Raetz, C. R. Eubacteria and archaea. In *Essentials of Glycobiology*, 2nd ed; Varki, A., Cummings, R. D., Esko, J. D., Freeze, H. H., Stanley, P., Bertozzi, C. R., Hart, G. W., Etzler, M. E. (Eds.); Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press: Cold Spring Harbor, New York, 2009, Vol.,
20. Ruiz, N.; Kahne, D.; Silhavy, T. J. *Nat Rev Micro*, **2009**, *7*, 677-683.
21. Erridge, C.; Bennett-Guerrero, E.; Poxton, I. R. *Microb. Infect.*, **2002**, *4*, 837-851.
22. Brown, S.; Santa Maria, J. P.; Walker, S. *Annu. Rev. Microbiol.*, **2013**, *67*, 313-336.
23. Brown, S.; Xia, G.; Luhachack, L. G.; Campbell, J.; Meredith, T. C.; Chen, C.; Winstel, V.; Gekeler, C.; Irazoqui, J. E.; Peschel, A.; Walker, S. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, **2012**, *109*, 18909-18914.
24. Sewell, E. W. C.; Brown, E. D. *J Antibiot*, **2014**, *67*, 43-51.
25. Xia, G.; Kohler, T.; Peschel, A. *Int. J. Med. Microbiol.*, **2010**, *300*, 148-154.
26. Kindt, T. J.; Osborne, B. A.; Goldsby, R. A. *Kuby Immunology*; W.H. Freeman & Company: New York, New York, 2007.
27. Tortora, G. J.; Funke, B. R.; Case, C. L. *Microbiology: an Introduction*; The Benjamin/Cummings Publishing Company, Inc.: Redwood City, California, 1992.
28. Taylor, C. M.; Roberts, I. S. Capsular Polysaccharides and Their Role in Virulence. In *Concepts in Bacterial Virulence*, ed; Russell, W., Herwald, H. (Eds.); Karger: Basel, 2005, Vol., pp 55-66.
29. Peeters, C. C. A. M.; Lagerman, P. R.; Weers, O. d.; Oomen, L. A.; Hoogerhout, P.; Beurret, M.; Poolman, J. T.; Reddin, K. M. Preparation of Polysaccharide-Conjugate Vaccines. In *Vaccine Protocols*, ed; Robinson, A., Hudson, M. J., Cranage, M. P. (Eds.); Humana Press Inc.: New Jersey, 2003, Vol., pp 153-173.
30. Bishop, C. T.; Jennings, H. J. Immunology of Polysaccharides. In *The polysaccharides*, ed; Aspinall, G. O. (Ed.), Academic Press: New York, New York, 1982, Vol. 1, pp 292-328.
31. Schleifer, K.-H. Phylum XIII. Firmicutes Gibbons and Murray 1978, 5 (Firmacutes [sic] Gibbons and Murray 1978, 5). In *Bergey's Manual® of Systematic Bacteriology*,

- ed; De Vos, P., Garrity, G., Jones, D., Krieg, N., Ludwig, W., Rainey, F., Schleifer, K.-H., Whitman, W. (Eds.); Springer New York: 2009, Vol., pp 19-1317.
32. Simpson, L. L. *Annu. Rev. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, **1986**, *26*, 427-453.
 33. Proft, T. *Bacterial Toxins: Genetics, Cellular Biology and Practical Applications*; Caister Academic Press: 2013.
 34. Barbut, F.; Petit, J. C. *Clin. Microbiol. Infect.*, **2001**, *7*, 405-410.
 35. Kuntz, J.; Chrischilles, E.; Pendergast, J.; Herwaldt, L.; Polgreen, P. *BMC Infect. Dis.*, **2011**, *11*, 194.
 36. Kachrimanidou, M.; Malisiovas, N. *Crit. Rev. Microbiol.*, **2011**, *37*, 178-187.
 37. Song, Y.; Liu, C.; Molitoris, D. R.; Tomzynski, T. J.; Lawson, P. A.; Collins, M. D.; Finegold, S. M. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.*, **2003**, *26*, 84-89.
 38. Bolte, E. R. *Medical Hypotheses*, **1998**, *51*, 133-144.
 39. *Bailey & Scott's Diagnostic Microbiology*; Mosby: St. Louis, Missouri, United States of America, 2007.
 40. Hatheway, C. L. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.*, **1990**, *3*, 66-98.
 41. Hart, G. B.; Strauss, M. B. *J. Hyperb. Med.*, **1990**, *5*, 125-144.
 42. Gas Gangrene. In *The Merck Manual of Medical Information*, ed; Beers, M. H. (Ed.), Merck & Co., Inc.: New Jersey, 2003, Vol., pp 1103.
 43. Urbina, P.; Flores-Díaz, M.; Alape-Girón, A.; Alonso, A.; Goni, F. M. *Chem. Phys. Lipids*, **2009**, *159*, 51-57.
 44. Onderdonk, A. B.; Garrett, W. S. Gas Gangrene and Other Clostridium-Associated Diseases. In *Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practices of Infectious Diseases*, ed; Mandell, G. L., Bennett, J. E., Dolin, R. (Eds.); Churchill Livingstone: New York, 2009, Vol., pp 3103-3109.
 45. Stevens, D. L.; Bisno, A. L.; Chambers, H. F.; Everett, E. D.; Dellinger, P.; Goldstein, E. J. C.; Gorbach, S. L.; Hirschmann, J. V.; Kaplan, E. L.; Montoya, J. G.; Wade, a. J. *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, **2005**, *41*, 1373-1406.
 46. Kalelkar, S.; Glushka, J.; Halbeek, v. H.; Morris, L. C.; Cherniak, R. *Carbohydr. Res.*, **1997**, *299*, 119-128.
 47. Sheng, S.; Cherniak, R. *Carbohydr. Res.*, **1997**, *305*, 65-72.
 48. Weintraub, A. *Carbohydr. Res.*, **2003**, *338*, 2539-2547.

49. Kaech, S. M.; Tan, J. T.; Wherry, E. J.; Konieczny, B. T.; Surh, C. D.; Ahmed, R. *Nat. Immunol.*, **2003**, *4*, 1191-1198.
50. Bernasconi, N. L.; Traggiai, E.; Lanzavecchia, A. *Science*, **2002**, *298*, 2199-2202.
51. Mäkelä, P. H.; Käyhty, H.; Leino, T.; Auranen, K.; Peltola, H.; Ekström, N.; Eskola, J. *Vaccine*, **2003**, *22*, 287-292.
52. Shelly, M. A.; Jacoby, H.; Riley, G. J.; Graves, B. T.; Pichichero, M.; Treanor, J. J. *Infect. Immun.*, **1997**, *65*, 242-247.
53. Jensen, F. Introduction to computational chemistry; John Wiley & Sons: 2013.
54. Roe, D. R.; Cheatham, T. E. *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation*, **2013**, *9*, 3084-3095.
55. Case, D. A.; Darden, T. A.; Cheatham, T. E.; Simmerling, C. L.; Wang, J.; Duke, R. E.; Luo, R.; Crowley, M.; Walker, R. C.; Zhang, W.; Merz, K. M.; Wang, B.; Hayik, S.; Roitberg, A.; Seabra, G.; Kolossvary, I.; Wong, K. F.; Paesani, F.; Vanicek, J.; Wu, X.; Brozell, S. R.; Steinbrecher, T.; Gohlke, H.; Yang, L.; Tan, C.; Mongan, J.; Hornak, V.; Cui, G.; Mathews, D. H.; Seetin, M. G.; Sagui, C.; Babin, V.; Kollman, P. A. Amber 10; University of California: 2008.
56. Cremer, D.; Pople, J. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **1975**, *97*, 1354-1358.
57. Sega, M.; Autieri, E.; Pederiva, F. *The Journal of chemical physics*, **2009**, *130*, 225102.
58. Babin, V.; Sagui, C. *The Journal of chemical physics*, **2010**, *132*, 104108.
59. Davies, G. J.; Planas, A.; Rovira, C. *Acc. Chem. Res.*, **2011**, *45*, 308-316.
60. Cross, S.; Kuttel, M. M.; Stone, J. E.; Gain, J. E. *J. Mol. Graphics Model.*, **2009**, *28*, 131-139.
61. Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K. *J. Mol. Graphics*, **1996**, *14*, 33-38.
62. National Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System for Enteric Bacteria (NARMS): Human Isolates Final Report, 2010; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, CDC: Atlanta, Georgia, 2012.
63. Mainous III, A. G.; Diaz, V. A.; Matheson, E. M.; Gregorie, S. H.; Hueston, W. J. *Public Health Rep*, **2011**, *126*, 354-360.
64. Spellberg, B.; Guidos, R.; Gilbert, D.; Bradley, J.; Boucher, H. W.; Scheld, W. M.; Bartlett, J. G.; Edwards, J. J.; American, I. D. S. o. *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, **2008**, *46*, 155-164.
65. Westphal, O.; Jann, K. General Polysaccharides. In *Methods in Carbohydrate Chemistry*, ed; Academic Press: New York, 1965, Vol. V, pp 83-91.

66. Haynes, W. M. CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 95th ed.; CRC Press: Boca Raton, Florida, 2014.
67. Sawardeker, J. S.; Sloneker, J. H.; Jeanes, A. *Anal. Chem.*, **1965**, *37*, 1602-1604.
68. Higgins, M. K.; Bly, R. S.; Morgan, S. L. *Anal. Chem.*, **1994**, *66*, 2656-2668.
69. Björndal, H.; Lindberg, B.; Pilotti, Å.; Svensson, S. *Carbohydr. Res.*, **1970**, *15*, 339-349.
70. Harris, D. C. Quantitative Chemical Analysis, 7th ed.; W. H. Freeman and Company: 2007.
71. Goldstein, I.; Hay, G.; Lewis, B. A.; Smith, F. *Methods in carbohydrate chemistry*, **1965**, *5*, 361-370.
72. Jacobsen, N. E. NMR Spectroscopy Explained; John Wiley & Sons, Inc.: New Jersey, 2007.
73. Vliegthart, J. F. G. Introduction to NMR Spectroscopy of Carbohydrates. In *NMR Spectroscopy and Computer Modeling of Carbohydrates*, ed; American Chemical Society: DC, 2006, Vol., pp 1-11.
74. Bubb, W. A. *Concepts in Magnetic Resonance Part A*, **2003**, *19A*, 1-19.
75. Agrawal, P. K. *Phytochemistry*, **1992**, *31*, 3307-3330.
76. Perlin, A. S.; Casu, B.; Koch, H. J. *Can. J. Chem.*, **1970**, *48*, 2596-2606.
77. Fulmer, G. R.; Miller, A. J.; Sherden, N. H.; Gottlieb, H. E.; Nudelman, A.; Stoltz, B. M.; Bercaw, J. E.; Goldberg, K. I. *Organometallics*, **2010**, *29*, 2176-2179.
78. Frisch, M. J.; Trucks, G. W.; Schlegel, H. B.; Scuseria, G. E.; Robb, M. A.; Cheeseman, J. R.; Scalmani, G.; Barone, V.; Mennucci, B.; Petersson, G. A.; Nakatsuji, H.; Caricato, M.; Li, X.; Hratchian, H. P.; Izmaylov, A. F.; Bloino, J.; Zheng, G.; Sonnenberg, J. L.; Hada, M.; Ehara, M.; Toyota, K.; Fukuda, R.; Hasegawa, J.; Ishida, M.; Nakajima, T.; Honda, Y.; Kitao, O.; Nakai, H.; Vreven, T.; Montgomery, J. A., Jr.; Peralta, J. E.; Ogliaro, F.; Bearpark, M.; Heyd, J. J.; Brothers, E.; Kudin, K. N.; Staroverov, V. N.; Kobayashi, R.; Normand, J.; Raghavachari, K.; Rendell, A.; Burant, J. C.; Iyengar, S. S.; Tomasi, J.; Cossi, M.; Rega, N.; Millam, M. J.; Klene, M.; Knox, J. E.; Cross, J. B.; Bakken, V.; Adamo, C.; Jaramillo, J.; Gomperts, R.; Stratmann, R. E.; Yazyev, O.; Austin, A. J.; Cammi, R.; Pomelli, C.; Ochterski, J. W.; Martin, R. L.; Morokuma, K.; Zakrzewski, V. G.; Voth, G. A.; Salvador, P.; Dannenberg, J. J.; Dapprich, S.; Daniels, A. D.; Farkas, Ö.; Foresman, J. B.; Ortiz, J. V.; Cioslowski, J.; Fox, D. J. Gaussian 09, Revision A.01; Gaussian, Inc.: Wallingford CT, 2009.
79. IUPAC-IUB Joint Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature (JCBN). *Eur. J. Biochem.*, **1983**, *131*, 5-7.

80. Pigman, W.; Isbell, H. S. *Advances in carbohydrate chemistry*, **1968**, *23*, 11-57.
81. Case, D. A.; Babin, V.; Berryman, J. T.; Betz, R. M.; Cai, Q.; Cerutti, D. S.; T.E. Cheatham, I.; Darden, T. A.; Duke, R. E.; Gohlke, H.; Goetz, A. W.; Gusarov, S.; Homeyer, N.; Janowski, P.; Kaus, J.; Kolossváry, I.; Kovalenko, A.; Lee, T. S.; LeGrand, S.; Luchko, T.; Luo, R.; Madej, B.; Merz, K. M.; Paesani, F.; Roe, D. R.; Roitberg, A.; Sagui, C.; Salomon-Ferrer, R.; Seabra, G.; Simmerling, C. L.; Smith, W.; Swails, J.; Walker, R. C.; Wang, J.; Wolf, R. M.; Wu, X.; Kollman, P. A. AMBER 14. University of California, San Francisco, 2014.
82. Kirschner, K. N.; Yongye, A. B.; Tschampel, S. M.; González-Outeiriño, J.; Daniels, C. R.; Foley, B. L.; Woods, R. J. *J. Comput. Chem.*, **2008**, *29*, 622-655.
83. Richards, M. R.; Bai, Y.; Lowary, T. L. *Carbohydr. Res.*, **2013**, *374*, 103-114.
84. Berendsen, H. J. C.; Postma, J. P. M.; van Gunsteren, W. F.; DiNola, A.; Haak, J. R. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, **1984**, *81*, 3684-3690.
85. Ryckaert, J.-P.; Ciccotti, G.; Berendsen, H. J. *Journal of Computational Physics*, **1977**, *23*, 327-341.
86. Jorgensen, W. L.; Chandrasekhar, J.; Madura, J. D.; Impey, R. W.; Klein, M. L. *The Journal of chemical physics*, **1983**, *79*, 926-935.
87. Adelman, S. A.; Doll, J. D. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, **1976**, *64*, 2375-2388.
88. R.Core.Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing* (R version 3.0.2). 2013: <http://www.R-project.org>.
89. Nychka, D.; Furrer, R.; Sain, S. *fields: Tools for spatial data* 2014: <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=fields>.
90. Robotham, A. *fields: sphereplot: Spherical plotting* 2013: <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=sphereplot>.
91. Adler, D.; Murdoch, D.; Nenadic, O.; Urbanek, S.; Chen, M.; Gebhardt, A.; Bolker, B.; Csardi, G.; Strzelecki, A.; Senger, A. *rgl: 3D visualization device system (OpenGL)* (R package version 0.93.996). 2014: <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rgl>.
92. Rocha-Pinto, H. J.; Observatório do Valongo - UFRJ. *Allsky projections in R* 2014: <https://sites.google.com/a/astro.ufrj.br/astronomer/home/allsky-projections-in-r>.
93. Cignoni, P.; Callieri, M.; Corsini, M.; Dellepiane, M.; Ganovelli, F.; Ranzuglia, G., in: Eurographics Italian Chapter Conference, The Eurographics Association, 2008, pp. 129-136.